

ALFA

UNLOCKING THE BIOGAS POTENTIAL
OF LIVESTOCK FARMING

D1.1

Framework and value chain conditions affecting the biogas in livestock farming

AzzeroCO2

31.03.2023

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ABBREVIATIONS

AD	Anaerobic Digestion
ARERA	Italian Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment
AU	Autorizzazione Unica (Measure for the authorisation of electricity production plants powered by RES)
CNG	Compressed Natural Gas
CHP	Combined Heat and Power (cogeneration)
CIC	Certificato di Immissione in Consumo (certificates for the use of biofuels in the transport sector)
DILA	Dichiarazione di Inizio Lavori Asseverata (Declaration/Communication of work)
EEG	Eneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz (Renewable Energy Sources Act)
EMD	Recast Electricity Market Directive
FiTs	Feed- In-Tariffs

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GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GSE	Gestore Servizi Energetici (Electric Services Manager)
GDP	Growth Domestic Product
GO	Guarantees of Origin
HABIO	Hellenic Association of Biogas Producers
INE	National Institute of Statistic of Spain's
LNG	Liquified Natural Gas
MITECO	Spanish Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge
NIMBY	Not In My Backyard
NPO-P	nitrogen and phosphorus plan (in Denmark)
PAS	Procedura Abilitativa Semplificata (Usable procedure for the construction of electricity production plants powered by RES below predetermined power thresholds)
PNRR	Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan
RED II	Renewable Energy Directive
SBA	Slovak Biogas Association
RES	Renewable Energy Source
ZUN	Vulnerable Areas to Nitrates

Executive Summary

The deliverable D1.1 “Framework and value chain conditions affecting biogas uptake in livestock farming” presents a comprehensive description of the state of play of biogas and biomethane market in Europe and in the six regions where the Alfa Hubs will be established (Greece, Italy, Denmark, Spain, Slovakia and Belgium).

ALFA project’s main objective is to tap the potential of biogas production from livestock farming to enhance the wider uptake of RES and increase the share of bioenergy as a baseload energy source, while ensuring reduced emissions from untreated animals’ waste and supporting the creation of new jobs and revenue for the livestock farming industry. During its three years, the project will support at least 50 livestock farmers in 6 EU countries (IT, DK, BE, SK, EL, ES) to overcome existing barriers and viably take up biogas solutions whilst providing a more informed basis for policy-makers and stakeholders by unveiling biogas market dynamics. Tools will be created to reduce investment risk and support more robust and efficient financial frameworks to allow massive scalability of biogas. ALFA will provide science-based information to livestock farming decision makers for the potential of biogas and raise the awareness of the general public on misperceptions about biogas and bioenergy.

In this context the current report describes the state of development of the biogas market dedicating one chapter to each of the 6 target Countries and one to the European context to better understand what condition can foster or hamper the diffusion of biogas and biomethane in the agriculture sector and in particular in livestock farming. Thus, the analysis is not limited to a description of the biogas market, of the number and dimension of the plants, of the substrate used, of the trend of installed power and of the overall potential, but goes through social aspects such as citizens’ awareness, the “not in my backyard” (NIMBY) effect and farmers knowledge economic aspects such as the farm dimensions and the cost of large plants, legal aspects related to the incentives schemes, to the authorization process, to the grid connection, the use of digestate etc.

1. Introduction

Production of biogas from livestock manure can help to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and support a more sustainable and circular bioenergy system. However, this potential is largely untapped mainly due to lack of awareness and support measures for market uptake.

ALFA aims to increase the use of biogas from livestock farming as a renewable energy source and reduce GHG emissions caused by the decomposition of animal waste. The project will support over 50 livestock farmers in adopting biogas solutions and provide information and tools to reduce investment risk and support financial frameworks to allow for scalability.

Moreover, ALFA intends to raise awareness of biogas and bioenergy among the general public and provide science-based information to livestock farming decision-makers. The project will be carried out in six representative European (EU) countries focusing on overcoming barriers to biogas adoption, such as limited awareness and inadequate financial frameworks. The ultimate goal is to enhance the wider uptake of renewable energy systems and increase the share of bioenergy as a baseload energy source.

By performing the intended actions, ALFA aims to reach the following goals:

- Analyse the state of play, identify regional differences, and investigate framework conditions to identify drivers and barriers to biogas adoption in the EU livestock farming industry;
- Co-create ALFA support measures which are replicable and effective in driving biogas adoption in the livestock farming industry in accordance with the identified needs and challenges;
- Deploy ALFA's biogas uptake support measures in real-world market conditions across European countries to facilitate the integration of renewable energy into their final energy consumption mix;
- Evaluate results and use evidence to communicate project results, provide policy recommendations, and promote mutual learning, and exploitation in order to scale the livestock biogas ecosystem across Europe.

In all respects, ALFA intends to improve understanding and social acceptance of biogas production facilities through a suite of educational material based on existing research findings, as well as to support livestock farmers and stakeholders in tackling barriers to the uptake of biogas systems and technology in the livestock farming industry. Additionally, ALFA will collaborate with relevant initiatives and provide tools to aid in the replication of its own project results, ensuring their long-term viability for supporting the uptake of circular bioeconomy practices.

The current report describes the framework conditions in the 6 target regions (Greece, Italy, Denmark, Spain, Slovakia and Belgium) dedicating one chapter to each of the 6 target countries and one to the European context to better understand what conditions can foster or hamper the market uptake of biogas and biomethane in the agriculture sector and in particular in livestock farming.

2. Methodology

This report aims to investigate the social, economic, legal and policy conditions under which biogas and biomethane issues are addressed in the target countries. All these aspects can represent a barrier or an enabler for the anaerobic digestion technology; a better understanding of the overall framework conditions will help partners to design the services for the National hubs and foster a wider diffusion of both biogas and biomethane in livestock farming.

To this end an in-depth desk research, based on previous research, reports, papers, official statistical data, etc., has been carried out by all the partners responsible for the organization of the 6 regional hubs (one for each target country) under the coordination of AzzeroCO2. The review was meant to reinforce the whole value chain and ease the market uptake by considering economic and social aspects, the authorization process and the legal aspects related to biogas (e.g. on the use of digestate), technical issues, and trying to relate these aspects to the potential to understand how they acted as an enabler or a barrier.

To complement the desk review and collect insights directly from value chain actors, 43 stakeholders have been interviewed: 9 Danish, 6 Spanish, 5 Belgians, 7 Italians, 9 Slovaks, 7 Greeks. Only five of the respondents are women, despite the effort to keep a gender balance, highlighting the lack of women professionals in the livestock farming industry and the biogas sector and particularly in the decision-making positions.

The interviews are based on 5 different questionnaires, each one designed for a specific stakeholder category: a) farmers/breeders that have a biogas plant, b) farmers that don't have it, c) banks or financial institutions, d) technology providers, experts and plant designers, e) public officers in charge for plant authorizations.

At the beginning of the report, a general European overview is also presented together with mapping at country level.

3. European Union

3.1 Overall context – The green transition

The ambitious European Union targets to achieve a 55% reduction in greenhouse gases by 2030, and to become the first climate neutral continent by 2050 (European Green Deal, 2020)¹ are closely related to the structural green revamp of the energy system. In particular, such decarbonization goal depends on the definitive uptake of the renewable energies, especially those that are already available, cost effective, and quickly scalable, like biogas and biomethane.

Biogas and biomethane are biomass-based, eco-friendly, and flexible energy sources. Their usage can minimize the GHG emissions in several sectors, such as transport, agriculture, industry, and buildings. Biogas usage mainly regards the electricity and heat generation, and household' activities (like cooking and heating). Through the biogas upgrading process or the thermal gasification of solid biomass followed by methanation, it is possible to obtain the biomethane. It can be injected into the gas grid or used as transport fuel, which is one of its main future purposes.

Figure 1: Installed capacity in Europe by source²

Biogas, biomethane, and renewable energies diffusion in Europe in the last decades is shown in Figure 1. Such graph represents the installed capacity expressed in GW by source in our continent (EMBER, 2023)². Renewables and biofuels utilization constantly increase over the observation period. On the contrary, the installed capacity related to non-renewable energy sources (i.e. gas, coal, and other fossil) has a downward trend since 2019, while the nuclear capacity remains quite stable.

¹ European Commission, 2020, European Green Deal, https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/european-green-deal_en

² EMBER, 2023, Countries and Regions, <https://ember-climate.org/countries-and-regions/regions/europe/>

Figure 2 shows the installed capacity percentages in 2021 in Europe. Renewables and biofuels presented their highest share (50.76%), followed by fossil (38.66%), and nuclear (10.57%).

In particular, only 2.67% of the installed capacity concerned bioenergy. Such context analysis highlights that although there has been an acceleration in recent years, sources such as biogas and biomethane are not fully exploited with respect to their great potential.

Figure 2: Percentage of Installed capacity in Europe by source in 2021. Elaboration using data contained in (EMBER, 2023)²

3.2 Biogas and Biomethane in Europe

3.2.1 General Overview

At the end of 2021, Europe had around 20,000 biogas and biomethane plants in operation, which production amounted to 196 TWh, equivalent to 18.4 bcm (billion cubic meters) of natural gas, as shown in Figure 3 (EBA statistical report, 2022)³. The European biogas plants were 18,843, while the biomethane plants were 1,067. From 2009 to 2015, the increase in number of biogas plants was significant. On the other hand, in the last period the biogas industry does not have remarkable growth. In fact, the biogas production stagnated between 2016 and 2021 around 158 TWh per year (ifeu, 2022)⁴. Such phenomenon is due to the fact that more European countries are shifting incentives from biogas production to biomethane production, resulting in sustained rapid expansion of the biomethane industry (Pavičić, 2022)⁵. Indeed, biomethane plants are exponentially increasing all over Europe, just like their annual growth. Compared to 2020, 184 plants were installed, and this makes 2021 the year with the largest increase in biomethane plants to date. It should also be noted that biomethane plants are averagely larger in size than biogas plants. Whereas a biogas plant produces on average 8 GWh per year, a biomethane plant produces an average of 35 GWh per year (EBA statistical report, 2022)³.

³ European Biogas Association, 2022, Statistical Report Tracking biogas and biomethane deployment across Europe 2022, https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/_trashed-3/

⁴ Nabil Abdalla, Silvana Bürck, Horst Fehrenbach, Susanne Köppen, Tim Janosch Staigl, 2022, Biomethane in Europe, ifeu - Institut für Energie und Umweltforschung, https://www.ifeu.de/fileadmin/uploads/ifeu_ECF_biomethane_EU_final_01.pdf

⁵ Pavičić, J., Novak Mavar, K., Brkić, V., & Simon, K., 2022, Biogas and Biomethane Production and Usage: Technology Development, Advantages and Challenges in Europe. *Energies*, 15(8), 2940

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Figure 3: Combined number of biomethane and biogas plants in Europe (above), combined biomethane and biogas energy production in Europe (TWh) (below) (EBA statistical report, 2022)³

By analysing the types of plants that produced biogas and biomethane in Europe in 2021 (Figure 4), the importance of agricultural installations is clear. In particular, the percentage of production from agricultural systems was equal to 64% both for biogas and biomethane. For biogas the second biggest production source was landfill (14%), while for biomethane were organic municipal solid waste (11%), and industrial products (11%). Finally, the sewage sludge was a useful source (7%-6%) for both (EBA statistical report)³.

Figure 4: Relative use of type of plants in Europe by source in 2021. Elaboration using data contained in (EBA statistical report, 2022)³

3.2.2 Energy produced by country

Always taking 2021 as a reference, the main biogas and biomethane producer in Europe was Germany with more than 80 TWh (42.79%) (Figure 5). The United Kingdom is included in this analysis and followed in second place (about 27 TWh, 13.38%). Italy was third having a production of almost 26 TWh (13.14%), but it was not in the first positions in terms of biomethane production. France held the fourth position, while Spain, Czech Republic, Poland, and Belgium were also relevant biogas producers, but had almost no biomethane production. In contrast, biomethane production was significantly high in Denmark and the Netherlands. In particular Denmark, Sweden, Norway and Estonia are to date the countries to report more biomethane than biogas production. Other Countries such as France, the Netherlands, Italy, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom are tending in this direction with targeted actions and choices (EBA conference, 2022)⁶.

Figure 5: Combined biomethane and biogas production per country in 2021 (GWh) (left), Percentage of combined

biomethane and biogas production in Europe in 2021 (right). Elaboration using data contained in (EBA statistical report, 2022)⁷

3.2.3 Number of plants by country

As seen, for combined biomethane and biogas production, Germany was leader in Europe for the number of biogas and biomethane installed plants in 2021 (Fig 6). The 12,573 energy systems represented 56.44% of the total in Europe. Italy and France held the second and third position with 1827 and 1310 plants, respectively. Outside the podium there was the United Kingdom with 1277 plants (6.41%). Regarding to the number of biomethane system, France was the leading nation (365), followed by Germany (238) and the UK (117).

Figure 6: Combined biomethane and biogas number of plants per country in 2021 (left), Percentage of combined biomethane and biogas number of plants in Europe in 2021 (right). Elaboration using data contained in (EBA statistical report, 2022)⁷

⁶ European Biogas Association, 2022, European Biogas conference 2022,

<https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/european-biogas-conference-2022/>

⁷ European Biogas Association, 2022, Statistical Report Tracking biogas and biomethane deployment across Europe 2022, https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/_trashed-3/

3.2.4 *Different policies and strategies*

Figure 5 and Figure 6 clearly reveal that biofuels have had different spreads in the European countries. Such phenomenon is closely linked to political choices, incentives, economic benefits, and action plans that each nation has adopted. Different measures, strategies and legislation have shown great effectiveness in the diffusion of biogas, regardless of its final use. Undoubtedly there are countries that represent virtuous example. For instance, Germany introduced in 2000 the Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG or Eneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz) (EEG, 2000)⁸, that had a huge impact by tripling the biogas production until 2002. The EEG has undergone several updates in 2004, 2009, 2012, 2014, and 2017. The number of biogas plants continued to increase at a fast pace by 2014, when there was a significant remuneration rates reduction (EEG, 2014)⁹. On the other hand, the United Kingdom has been developing the biogas sector since the 1990s. In fact, in 1989 indirect subsidies for biogas production via the Non-fossil Fuel Obligation were introduced and the electricity supply companies had to provide a certain quantity of electricity generated from non-fossil sources. Several measures followed one another in the following years, for example the Electricity Act in 2002, and the Energy Act in 2008. All of these provisions have proven to be effective for the renewable energies and biofuels uptake. Another positive example is certainly France, which adopted winning measures for biogas development and recently has strongly focused on biomethane (EBA strategies, 2022)¹⁰. In particular, France began subsidizing its biogas sector with the Renewable Energy Feed-in Tariffs in 2001. The support system was revised in 2002, 2006, 2011, 2016, and 2020. The evolution of a favourable regulatory framework has nudged the growth of the biogas sector over the past two decades. Moreover, biogas producers in France can receive support from the French Environment & Energy Management Agency (ADEME), as well as from local authorities, for studies and investment (EBA statistical report, 2022)¹¹.

On the contrary other countries did not implement integrated and structured plans to foster the biofuels sector and inevitably hampered the value chain advancement. For example, in Latvia the government has frequently modified the existing legislation over the last years, creating a sense of confusion that has hindered the investments in renewable energy production plants. Slovenia is another representative case. Several other reasons contributed to a scarce diffusion of biomethane plants in some European Countries, such as Portugal, Lithuania, Serbia and Ukraine: no interest in investment (cheap energy from fossil fuels), no possibilities for investment in new technologies (lack of money), lack of awareness and information, absence of state subventions in the past for biomethane plants, lack of equipment, supplies, and know how in biogas technologies (EBA statistical report, 2022)¹¹.

⁸ The Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety, 2000, Renewable Energy Sources Act, <http://large.stanford.edu/courses/2016/ph240/barry2/docs/res-act.pdf>

⁹ The Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety, 2014, Renewable Energy Sources Act - RES Act 2014, https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/EN/Downloads/renewable-energy-sources-act-eeeg-2014.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=1

¹⁰ European Biogas Association, 2022, Manual for National Biomethane Strategies, https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/2022-Manual-for-National-Biomethane-Strategies_Gas-for-Climate.pdf

¹¹ European Biogas Association, 2022, Statistical Report Tracking biogas and biomethane deployment across Europe 2022, https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/_trashed-3/

3.3 Future perspectives

In 2022, Europe has taken concrete actions to scale up the biogas and biomethane sector, presenting the REPowerEU plan (REPowerEU, 2022)¹², and launching the Biomethane Industrial Partnership (BIP, 2022)¹³. Knowing that 18.4 bcm of biogas and biomethane were produced in EU in 2021 (EBA methane, 2022)¹⁴, the main target established by the EU is to achieve 35 bcm annual production and use of sustainable biomethane by 2030, and consequently to create the preconditions for a further ramp-up of its potential towards 2050. Several studies predict that the biomethane production in 2050 will be equals to 123 bcm¹¹ (without considering gasification). This production will mainly result from sequential crops, agricultural residues, and manure compared to other waste such as food waste, industrial wastewater, and sewage sludge (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Illustration of total biomethane production potential per feedstock type in 2050. Elaboration using data contained in (EBA statistical report, 2022)¹¹ 11

Such a growth has also had a huge impact in terms of employment. In fact, the biogas and biomethane industries are already responsible for about 220,000 jobs today, and reliable forecasts estimate a total of approximately 460,000 jobs by 2030 and over one million jobs by 2050 (EBA report, 2022)¹⁵. In recent years, several studies have also predicted the European biomethane and biogas production potential for 2030 and 2050 (Table 1: European biomethane and biogas production potential for 2030 and 2050, as estimated by different studies. Table 1).

¹² European Commission, 2022, REPowerEU: A plan to rapidly reduce dependence on Russian fossil fuels and fast forward the green transition*, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/e%20n/ip_22_3131

¹³ Biomethane Industrial Partnership, 2022, <https://bip-europe.eu/>

¹⁴ European Biogas Association, 2022, Breaking Free of the Energy Dependency Trap – Delivering 35 bcm of biomethane by 2030, <https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/REPowerEU-with-biomethane-EBA.pdf>

¹⁵ European Biogas Association, 2022, Biomethane production potentials in the EU - A Gas for Climate report, https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/GfC_national-biomethane-potentials_070722.pdf

Table 1: European biomethane and biogas production potential for 2030 and 2050, as estimated by different studies.

Study	Biomethane and biogas production potential (bcm)	Biomethane and biogas production potential (TWh)
Current Production		
	18.4	196
2030		
Eurogas¹⁶	35	375
European Commission¹⁷	44	467
Gas for Climate¹⁵	45	479
2050		
IEA¹⁸	125	1326
Eurogas	95	1008
Gas for Climate	165	1751

¹⁶ Eurogas, European Carbon Neutrality: The importance of gas, 2020, <https://www.europeangashub.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/DNV-GL-Eurogas-Report-Reaching-European-Carbon-Neutrality-Full-Report.pdf>

¹⁷ European Commission, 2016, Optimal use of biogas from waste streams. An assessment of the potential of biogas from digestion in the EU beyond 2020, https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2017-03/ce_delft_3q84_biogas_beyond_2020_final_report_0.pdf

¹⁸ International Energy Agency, 2020, Outlook for biogas and biomethane: Prospects for organic growth, <https://www.iea.org/reports/outlook-for-biogas-and-biomethane-prospects-for-organic-growth>

4. Country: Greece

4.1 State of biogas and biomethane in livestock farming

Greece is an agricultural country producing a considerable amount of crop residues as well as livestock manure. In Greece, farm animals produce a substantial number of residues, as livestock farming is highly mature. The Greek livestock system constitutes predominantly of sheep, goats, cows and calves, swine, and pullets, with poultry, sheep and goats breeding representing the highest percentage of livestock industry (Vlyssides, 2015)¹⁹.

In Greece, the agricultural residues dominate the Greek biogas market. To produce biogas from agriculture-based plants, Greece used 1,867,000 tons wet weight in 2021, with 88% of the agricultural feedstocks were made up of agricultural residues such as manure. Sequential crops make up 5% of the feedstocks and 11% is attributed to energy crops, as shown in Figure 8 (EBA statistical report, 2022)²⁰.

Figure 8: Share of different types of feedstock usage for biogas production in Greece in 2020 (EBA statistical report, 2022)²⁰

Biogas production in Greece began in the early 2000s, and for a decade the Greek biogas sector was dominated by sewage-based and landfill-based plants. Overall, the combined biogas production from these two sources grew from 543 GWh in 2011 to 717 GWh in 2021. Regarding biogas from the agriculture and livestock sector (below in Figure 9, both are included in green colour and labelled “Agricultural”), the first biogas production was in 2011 and reached 465GWh in 2021²⁰. Thus, the upward trend in the factories is expected to be maintained, in the next years.

Figure 9: Development of biogas production (GWh) (left), and development of number of biogas plants (right) (EBA statistical report, 2022)²⁰

¹⁹ Vlyssides A., Barampouti E. A., Mai S., 2015, Energy generation Potential in Greece from Agricultural Residues and Livestock Manure by Anaerobic Digestion Technology, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283096513_Energy_Generation_Potential_in_Greece_From_Agricultural_Residues_and_Livestock_Manure_by_Anaerobic_Digestion_Technology

²⁰ European Biogas Association, 2022, Statistical Report Tracking biogas and biomethane deployment across Europe 2022, https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/_trashed-3/

Regarding the biomethane potential, currently it is not commercially available, as there is no biomethane market in Greece. In the next years, no significant growth is expected in this area despite the big potential for supply of biomethane on the Greek islands (REGATRACE, 2020)²¹. Nonetheless, according to estimations for 2030 (Figure 10), some biomethane production is expected in Greece, but much lower than 2 bcm/year, as presented below for anaerobic digestions and thermal gasification as available technologies (EBA report, 2022)²².

Figure 10: Biomethane potential in 2030 per technology and country (EBA report, 2022)²²

The animal waste spreading in Greek rural areas comes mainly from medium and large-scale animal farms that are placed all over the country. In principle, the animal farms in Greek rural areas are small-scale and most of them are located in Central Macedonia (Thessaloniki, Imathia), Epirus (Ioannina), Thessaly and Attica, and they are overall representing a 55.6% of the total national amount in animal wastes production (Skoulou, V., Zabaniotou, A., 2007)²³. In 2020 there were 1,968,667 livestock farms in total, with or without biogas systems, reduced by 18.2 % compared to 2009 (2,406,683 livestock farms) (ELSTAT, 2021)²⁴. The Table 2 below presents the number of farmed animals by species.

Table 2: Number of farmed animals by species ((ELSTAT, 2021)²⁴

Type of animals	2009	2021
Cattle	648,067	624,397
Sheep	9,156,821	7,721,644
Goats	4,213,230	3,148,976
Pigs	947,222	742,963
Poultry	36,767,565	26,962,120

²¹ REGATRAGE (H2020 project GA 857795), 2020, Mapping the state of play of Renewable gases in Europe, <https://www.regatrace.eu/work-packages/wp6-support-for-biomethane-market-uptake/>

²² European Biogas Association, 2022, Biomethane Production potentials in the EU 2022, https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/GfC_Biomethane-potentials_2022.pdf

²³ Skoulou, V., Zabaniotou, A.: Investigation of agricultural and animal wastes in Greece and their allocation to potential application for energy production. Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev. 11, 1698–1719 (2007)

²⁴ ELSTAT, 2021, Results of the 2021 Agriculture-Livestock Census, https://www.statistics.gr/el/2021_agricultural-livestock-census-results

Additionally, according to ELSTAT and Vlyssides et al. the total manure amount was up to 29,952,500t/y in Greece in 2015, as presented below in the Table 3.

Table 3: Number of animals and animal waste production in Greek farms in annual basis (Number of animals sourced by ELSTAT, residue/ animal sourced by Vlyssides et al., 2015)²⁵

Animal Species	Number of animals	Residue/animal (tn/head)	Residues (tn)
Cattle	624,397	11.16	6,968,270.52
Pigs	742,963	1.34	995,570.42
Poultry	26,962,120	0.04	1,078,484.8
Goats and sheep	10,870,620	1.2	13,044,744

According to the latest statistical data from the European Biogas Association, in Greece there are overall 67 operational biogas plants sourcing different kinds of biomass. Based on own calculations using the Hellenic Association of Biogas Producers infographic (BioenergyNews, 2022) in Greece there is a total of 47.9MWel total power from biogas and produced power from 150kWel to 5,250 kWel per unit²⁶. Regarding the biogas production from the agricultural sector specifically the total power is 22,274 kWel with 26 units in Greece, averaging 856kWel power per unit in average (Bioenergynews, 2018)²⁶. The picture below presents the biomass stations in northern Greece according to RAE Geo portal (RAE, 2023)²⁷ related to their status (installation permit, rejected, operational, etc.).

Figure 11: Biomass stations in Northern Greece, Background Google Satellite (RAE, 2023)²⁷

²⁵ Vlyssides A., Barampouti E. A., Mai S., 2015, Energy generation Potential in Greece from Agricultural Residues and Livestock Manure by Anaerobic Digestion Technology, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283096513_Energy_Generation_Potential_in_Greece_From_Agricultural_Residues_and_Livestock_Manure_by_Anaerobic_Digestion_Technology

²⁶ Bioenergynews.gr, [Map with Biogas Facilities](https://www.bioenergynews.gr), 2018

²⁷ RAE (Regulatory Authority for Energy) Geo Portal

Despite the increased share of bioenergy in the last decade, the Greek energy sector still largely depends on fossil fuels, most of which are imported, with energy needs being predominantly covered by petroleum products, natural gas, lignite and renewable energy sources (DAPEEP, 2022)²⁸.

The figure in the right (Figure 12) and the table right below (Table 4) show the energy mix for the energy production in Greece for 2021. In total, biomass energy accounted for 490GWh and represented 0.91% of the total production, however the contribution of bioenergy in the electricity generation is scheduled to reach 1,600GWh by 2030 (REGATRACE, 2020)²⁹.

Figure 12: Production Mix, Greece, 2021 (DAPEEP, 2022)²⁸

Table 4: Production Mix, Greece, 2021 (RAE, 2021)³⁰

2021	Lignite	Oil	Natural Gas	Fossil Fuels Unspecified	Sum of Fossil Fuels	Solar	Wind	Hydro	Biomass	RES Unspecified	Sum of RES	Total
%	9.93 %	7.42 %	41.01 %	0.15 %	58.52 %	9.63 %	19.93 %	11.02 %	0.91 %	0.00 %	41.48 %	100.00 %
TWh	5.34	3.99	22.06	0.08	31.47	5.18	10.72	5.93	0.49	0.00	22.31	53.78

Regarding the main biogas production technologies in Greece, the method of anaerobic digestion is mostly used, whereby biomass, organic sub-sludge and waste, is decomposed in the absence of oxygen, and in the presence of bacteria, the organic matter is broken down and a mixture of gases, named biogas, is released. Biogas batch-reactors are used for this process. To produce biomethane, biogas must be upgraded, although it is a technology that is currently not applied in Greece (HABIO, 2022)³¹.

As in Europe so in Greece, for the utilization of biogas for heat and energy production, cogeneration is used, so the heat can be directly utilised by the unit itself, whereas the energy produced can be injected into the electricity grid (DAPEEP, 2021)³². On the other hand, biomethane could be fed into the natural gas network, as the existing infrastructure can receive biomethane, and can be used in a similar way to natural gas, alongside in transport sector as a substitute for CNG (Compressed Natural Gas) or LNG (Liquified Natural Gas) (DAPEEP, 2022)³². However, as it has already been stated there is no biomethane market for Greece yet.

²⁸ DAPEEP, 2022, Renewable Energy Sources Operator and Guarantees of Origin, [Residual Energy Mix 2021 \(short version – results only\)](#)

²⁹ REGATRAGE (H2020 project GA 857795) , 2020, Mapping the state of play of Renewable gases in Europe, <https://www.regatrace.eu/work-packages/wp6-support-for-biomethane-market-uptake/>

³⁰ RAE (Regulatory Authority for Energy) Geo Portal

³¹ HABIO (Hellenic Association of Biogas Producers), 2022, [Regarding the biogas and the biomethane](#)

³² DAPEEP, 2021, Renewable Energy Sources Operator and Guarantees of Origin, [Residual Energy Mix 2021 \(short version – results only\)](#)

4.2 Legal and policy framework

In Greece there is a common legal framework for the authorization of any type of RES, and not only for biogas plants. Specifically, the Law 4685/2020, offers an automated process for the Producer Certification through the new Electronic Register of Electricity Production from RES and CHP and replaces the previous Law 3468/2006. The Law 4685/2020 follows the EU Directive 2018/2001, for authorization process in two years, maximum three. The authorities responsible for the authorization are presented below (Table 5) alongside the main steps (Ministry of environment and Energy, 2023)³³ (Regulatory Authority for Energy, 2023)³⁴.

Table 5: Main steps for the authorization process and authorities involved (Regulatory Authority for Energy, 2023)³⁴

Steps	Responsible authority
Producer Certification	Regulatory Authority for Energy
Environmental License	Respective Region or Ministry of Environment or Energy
Granting a Final Connection Offer	Independent power transmission Operator or Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator
Installation Permit	Respective Region or Ministry of Environment or Energy
Sale of Electricity – Participation in the market, sign a contract	Renewable Energy Sources Operator & Guarantees of Origin Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator Electricity Suppliers Bodies for Collective Representation of RES
Operating License, after the trial operation	Respective Region or Ministry of Environment or Energy

4.2.1 Incentives schemes

In Greece, the different financial incentives schemes are generally regulated by the Developmental Laws, which also accommodate investments in the RES and the bioenergy sector of course in turn. The main forms of incentives are tax exemptions (exemption from paying income tax on realized pre-tax profits), subsidies (the State covers part of the investment) and leasing subsidies (the State covers part of the leasing for equipment needed, although only under specific conditions) (Giannousi, 2012)³⁵.

³³ Ministry for the Environment and Energy, 2020, [Authorization Process fro RES](#)

³⁴ RAE (Regulatory Authority for Energy), 2023, [Legal Fremewrok for RES, Information Note](#)

³⁵ Giannousi P., 2012, Financing biogas projects in Greece through the New Investment Law 3908/11, http://www.cres.gr/kape/publications/pdf/biogazin_prevaza/03_P.Giannousi_BiogasIN_200712_Preveza.pdf

4.2.2 Related legal aspects

The main legal framework in Greece regarding the RES is the National Energy and Climate plan, with the ultimate goal to reach the energy and climate targets for 2030, following the European legal framework (Ministry for the Environment and Energy, 2019)³⁶. Additionally, the Law 3851/2010 “Accelerating the development of Renewable Energy Sources to deal with climate change and other regulations addressing issues under the authority of the Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change”, offers a positive legal framework as well as financial elements for the development of successful biogas units (Zarifis C., 2016)³⁷.

4.2.3 Policy priorities

At the moment, through the new Central Agricultural Policy, two new programs are envisaged in Greece, one with a 50% subsidy and one with a 70% subsidy. The first program with 50% support has to do with the self-production of energy from RES to meet the needs of the farms or through the utilization of biomass, in the context of the classic Improvement Plans. The maximum budget that can be supported is 150,000 euros. The program with support of up to 70% is more specialized as it supports investments for the increase of sustainable energy (biomass utilization and biogas production), the production of energy from RES for self-consumption and the saving of energy in agricultural sector (Agronews, 2023)³⁸.

During the "Renewable / Storage Forum" conference, the President of HABIO (Hellenic Association of Biogas Producers) proposed the biogas units as a means of storage for the electrical system, while he highlighted that they should be prioritized for connection to the grid, and he also proposed simplification of the licensing and authorisation process (Ecopress, 2021)³⁹.

The production of biomethane and its use in the automotive sector or to feed the gas grid is not considered a policy priority in Greece at least in the next 5 or 10 years.

4.3 Socioeconomic aspects

4.3.1 Economic aspects

In 2010, the Greek government integrated FiTs (Feed- In-Tariffs) into its 3851 Renewable Energy Law, and a new tariff on agriculture-based biogas plants (up to 220 euro/MWh) was created. As a result, agricultural biogas production slowly began in Greece, with the first biogas from agriculture being produced in 2011. In 2016, the Greek government indicated new feed in tariff prices for the agricultural-based biogas plants (up to 225 euro/MWh). This of course led to an additional increase of such plants. Greece finally reached an agriculture biogas production of 465 GWh in 2021 (EBA, 2022)⁴⁰.

³⁶ Ministry for Environment and Energy, 2019, , [National Energy and Climate Plan](#), ΦΕΚ 4893/Β/2019, (2019)

³⁷ Zarifis C., CRES (Center for renewable energy sources and saving), [Biogas in Greece: Actual situation and perspectives](#), 2016

³⁸ Agronews, 2023, [Biogas and photovoltaics for energy autonomy in the Commission's plan](#)

³⁹ Ecopress.gr, 2021, [Biogas units help in the energy transition](#)

⁴⁰ European Biogas Association, 2022, Biomethane Production potentials in the EU 2022, https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/GfC_Biomethane-potentials_2022.pdf

4.3.2 Social aspects

It is a fact that the production and exploitation of biogas stimulates the local labour market, since it is produced decentrally and mainly outside of urban centres. The table below (Table 6) summarizes the labor market in the biogas sector for Greece.

Table 6: Average employment rate (jobs/GWh of biogas) (Vlyssides, 2015)⁴¹

Country	Year estimation of	Direct jobs (jobs/GWh)	Indirect jobs (jobs/GWh)	Total jobs (jobs/GWh)
Greece	2020	0.85	0.65	1.50

While according to the Hellenic Statistical Authority the distribution of the workers in livestock farming in 2020 (Table 7) was:

Table 7: Distribution of workers in the livestock farming (ELSTAT, 2021)⁴²

	Members of the family	Permanent workers	Temporary workers	Others
Days of work	12,373,277	1,299,304	3,268,148	445,951

Although underrepresented, women play a pivotal role in the agricultural and livestock farming, accounting for 39.7% of the agricultural workforce in Greece in 2013. Notably, the young people in farming take up only 10.2% for men and 4.5% for women in 2013 (Ministry of Interiors, 2018)⁴³.

Regarding the social acceptance of biomass powerplants in Greece, the main bottleneck in such projects was the NIMBY (not in my backyard) phenomenon and the lack of knowledge, however according to Mavrovouniotou, 33% of people accepted the potential of a biomass power plant in their region. The feasibility of a biomass plant projected is influenced by knowledge and/or lack of knowledge (Mavrovouniotou, 2014)⁴⁴.

4.4 Overall assessment

Greece has an enormous potential of unused biomass from animal residues and waste, which could be used in local plants for biogas production, without considerable transport needs. However, the availability of the feedstock, the fragmented supply chain, the bureaucracy (efforts for simplification of the process are being put, but there is still a long way to go), the insufficient financial incentives for small farms, the inefficient legal framework and the difficulty to address small-scale farms with small-scale technological solutions are some of the factors that at the moment hinder the biomass exploitation for energy production reasons. Apart from that, from a social perspective, the immense lack of knowledge on potential solutions and their benefits along with the considerable ignorance of the damage that the untreated manure poses to the environment, combined with the NIMBY phenomenon still set aside the market uptake of biogas solutions.

⁴¹ Vlyssides A., Barampouti E. A., Mai S., 2015, Energy generation Potential in Greece from Agricultural Residues and Livestock Manure by Anaerobic Digestion Technology, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283096513_Energy_Generation_Potential_in_Greece_From_Agricultural_Residues_and_Livestock_Manure_by_Anaerobic_Digestion_Technology

⁴² ELSTAT, 2021, Results of the 2021 Agriculture-Livestock Census, https://www.statistics.gr/el/2021_agricultural-livestock-census-results

⁴³ Ministry of Interior, 2018, [The Greek women farmer](#)

⁴⁴ Mavrovouniotou S., 2014 [Social Acceptance of biomass projects](#)

5. Country: Spain

5.1 State of biogas and biomethane in livestock farming

Agriculture is one of Spain's strategic sectors of great social, territorial, environmental, and economic relevance. Half of the land in the country is used for agricultural and/or livestock activities, making the agrifood sector one of the most dynamic ones in Spanish economy.

In 2017, the agricultural sector in Spain represented the fifth largest contribution to the country's growth domestic product (GDP), which highlights the importance of the sector for the country's economy in the latest years. Also, in terms of landscape, Spain was the 2nd country in the EU with more hectares dedicated to agriculture (2,437,891), only surpassed by France (2,548,677) in 2020 (EPDATA,2021)⁴⁵, (Statista, 2020)⁴⁶.

Through the overview provided by the National Institute of Statistic (INE) of Spain's 2020 Agricultural census, a number of 914,817 agricultural exploitation sites and 169,576 livestock farming sites were accounted for (NSI, 2020)⁴⁷. The report highlighted that few young people were fulfilling the roles of exploitation managers in the farms, with no more than 40% of them being under 45 years old. Regarding gender balance, the presence of female exploitation managers was low compared to males, not reaching more than 32% in most of the autonomous communities. In addition, regarding professional training, the percentage of these managers that have been formally trained was lower than 25% (NSI overview, 2020)⁴⁸.

Going over more specific data, when referring to livestock, poultry represented the biggest percentage of headage (138,617,508 headcount), followed by laying hens and pigs, as shown below in Figure 13 (NSI overview, 2020)⁴⁸⁴⁸.

Figure 13: Livestock headcount by animal species in Spain (2020) (NSI overview, 2020)⁴⁸⁴⁸

⁴⁵ EPDATA, 2021, El sector agrícola de España en el contexto Europeo, gráficos y estadísticas

⁴⁶ Statista, 2020, Area of organic agricultural land in Europe in 2020, by country

⁴⁷ National Statistics Institute, 2020, Censo Agrario 2020 [Agriculture Census 2020]

⁴⁸ National Statistics Institute, 2020, Panorámica del Censo Agrario 2020 [Overview of Agricultural Census 2020]

In order to evaluate the relevance of each species for the total livestock production, the graph on the right (Figure 14) and the measurements below were done using livestock units (LSU), which is a unit determined via specific coefficients by animal type, taking into consideration their nutritional requirements (NSI overview, 2020)⁴⁸. Even when the head count is higher for poultry as seen in Figure 13, pigs are the species with the highest weight in the livestock farming load, applicable for all autonomous communities in Spain, except for the north of the country where bovine farming remains the most relevant.

Figure 14 Livestock units per species in Spain (2020)

Looking then at the picture from the biogas perspective, in Spain the number of plants has grown exponentially over the last decade. Despite having great potential of biomass resources by generating around 49 million tons of livestock waste annually plus 7 million tons of food waste and 9 million tons of agricultural waste (figures from 2021), the country is at the bottom of the biomethane and biogas generation when comparing it with their European counterparts (Smallops, 2021)⁴⁹.

On 2022, the Spanish Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO) published [Spain's Biogas Roadmap](#) to serve as guidelines of action to multiply the sustainable production of biogas to achieve the targets set for 2050 towards climate neutrality. However, Spain still has very lax regulations regarding biogas, these mostly encouraging wind and photovoltaic energy projects, leaving biogas out of the picture (Smallops, 2021)⁴⁹ (MITECO, 2022)⁵⁰.

According to the registered data from MITECO as of 2020, Spain has 146 biogas installations, out of which 130 reported using biogas in 2020 (MITECO, 2022)⁵¹. The distribution of these installations is irregular throughout the country, with most being in Catalonia, Madrid, and Castilla y León, for both biogas and biomethane (Genia, 2020)⁵². The estimated production of these plants for 2020 was around 2.7TWh, and out of that total, 2.45TWh were consumed in electricity generation centrals. Out of these plants, 46 are associated to waste treatment, 34 to sewage treatment, 13 to agriculture, 3 to the production of beverages, 3 to the chemical industry, 7 to the paper industry, 1 to construction and 13 to administration, commerce, and other services. Regarding biomethane, the country has 5 plants for its production from biogas purification, and out

⁴⁹ Smallops, 2021, Situation of Biogas in Spain and Europe

⁵⁰ Spain's Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO), 2022, El MITECO saca a información pública la propuesta de Hoja de Ruta del Biogás [MITECO publishes publicly their proposal for the Biogas Roadmap]

⁵¹ Spain's Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO), 2022, Hoja de Ruta del Biogás [Biogas Roadmap]

⁵² Genia bioenergy, "Mapa de plantas de biogás en España. Cada vez más empresas se unen a la producción de biometano," [Online]. <https://geniabienergy.com/plantas-biogas-en-espana/>.

of those, 4 are of recent creation (between the last months of 2021 and beginning of 2022) (MITECO, 2022)⁵³.

The country's biogas roadmap focuses around biogas produced via anaerobic digestion due to the high level of maturity of the technology available when compared with other production processes. However, even though the technology is readily available, the operation needed to produce biogas, biomethane, and high-quality digestate can be complex and costly (MITECO, 2022)⁵¹. In addition to this, in the case of biomethane a posterior process is needed for biogas upgrading, adding a layer of complexity to the equation.

5.2 Legal and policy framework

In line with the European framework, the government has also produced [Spain's Strategy for Circular Economy](#) (NSI, 2020)⁵⁴ which includes a drop of 15% of waste in regard to the figures from 2010 as one of the goals and guidance to implement the principle of waste hierarchy, which is especially relevant because the biogas technologies can play an essential role in biowaste management (NSI, 2020)⁵⁵.

Also, the [National Plan for the Integration of Energy and Climate \(PNIEC\)](#) (Smallops, 2021)⁵⁶ also published by MITECO for the 2021-2030 period, promotes renewable gas via measure 1.8 of the document, promoting the authorization of specific plans and biogas uptake in general, including biogas, biomethane and renewable hydrogen (also supported by [Legislation 7/2021](#)). In addition, other measures stated in the PNIEC document, like 1.21 and 1.22, include a series of actions to aid the efficient management of methane waste and the energy valorisation of the biogas (NSI, 2020)^{55,47}.

Although the previously mentioned plans focus more looking towards 2030, In the country there are also strategies set looking forward into 2050's climate neutrality, such as the [Strategy for Decarbonization in the Long Run \(ELP 2050\)](#). In this strategy, biogas is present especially for the analysis in the agricultural, livestock and waste sectors. For agriculture & livestock, the document gathers the biogas production for the different working lines as considered to achieve the goals for 2050 to reduce emissions successfully. Then, for waste, it states that the implementation of mature technologies will be boosted, such as composting, anaerobic digestion and biogas capture.

5.2.1 Authorization process for instalment of biogas system and for the injection on the grid

An authorization process specific for biogas plants and valid throughout the country is still missing, it is each autonomic community that defines the requirements, fees and procedures for the approval of a plant. This has become a great barrier, because each community has its own procedures, often deemed as very complex and not standardized at all. In the framework proposed in Spain's Biogas Roadmap, the regulatory instruments proposed and expected in the next future are:

⁵³ Spain's Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO), 2022, Hoja de Ruta del Biogás [Biogas Roadmap]

⁵⁴ National Statistics Institute, 2020, Panorámica del Censo Agrario 2020 [Overview of Agricultural Census 2020]

⁵⁵ National Statistics Institute, 2020, Censo Agrario 2020 [Agriculture Census 2020]

⁵⁶ Smallops, 2021, Situation of Biogas in Spain and Europe

- Valorizing the renewable origin of biogas
 - [Implementation of the Guarantee of Origin](#) (May 2022): This will ease the verification of the percentage of energy coming from renewable gas of providers' supply structures or of the energy supplied for consumers. The necessary normative was developed by MITECO to define a Guarantee of Origin system, which now allows suppliers and consumers to be able to differentiate between biogas and fossil-based gas.
- Simplification of administrative procedures and elimination of regulatory barriers
 - Speeding up authorization process of plants and other associated infrastructures/processes: One of the main barriers for the country is the processing time and the high complexity of the authorization process, due to these being applicable to many normatives, such as waste, agriculture, animal and crop health, industrial, gas emissions, sounds and odours normatives, among many others. For this, a process specifically for the authorization of biogas plants will be developed, reducing considerably steps and waiting time. For this, the capacity of the technical personnel in charge of authorizing will be built.
 - Homogenization of administrative procedures among autonomic communities: In Spain, each autonomic community has autonomy over a very broad part of laws, and they can be particular and different for each community. Of course, this has also been a barrier for biogas, because the procedures per community are not similar. To palliate this, a collaboration with autonomic and regional authorities must come in place to establish a common procedure for the authorization of construction of biogas plants.
 - Development of an authorization process guide: A catalogue will be elaborated to gather requirements, procedures and processes to obtain the desired authorization to serve as guide for competent administrative bodies to clarify the current uncertainty around the processes.

5.2.2 Incentives schemes

Regarding renewable energy sources, in 2021 MITECO (with the collaboration of IDEA, and NextGeneration EU funding) implemented a series of incentive schemes for renewable energies for self-consumption (900M€), storage (220M€) and thermal systems for climatization (200M€) in the residential sector (scheme valid until 2023). This incentive programme was directed to individuals or enterprises performing an economic activity, e.g; industrial polygon managers, companies with energy-related activities, ESCOs, among others, having a strong a focus on eolic and solar energy, but not excluding biogas and bioethanol (IDEA 2021)⁵⁷.

No incentive schemes specific for farmers have been identified at the moment regarding implementation of biogas or biomethane, and the interviewees were not aware of any, either.

For companies with biogas projects, the only incentive scheme identified directly addressing biogas was the *Programme of Incentives for Single Projects on Biogas Installation*, managed also by the IDEA and MITECO through the NextGeneration EU framework. The first open call was launched in 2022 and closed around October, and the funds were awarded on a competitive basis to the projects with the best scores. The total fund of 150M euro will be divided considering a maximum grant of 15M euro for project/company, and a minimum inversion of 100,000 euros (IDEA, 2022)⁵⁷

⁵⁷ IDEA, 2022, Programa de Incentivos a Proyectos Singulares de Instalaciones de Biogás [Programme of Incentives for Single Projects on Biogas Installation]

This programme seeks to boost the use of anaerobic digestion for biogas production to obtain biomethane and also electricity, also collaborating with the heat and cold demand. The call prioritises projects that have a positive impact on communities, SMEs, and also the ones that consider the social component and gender balance (IDEA, 2022)⁵⁷.

5.2.3 Related legal aspects

The following aspects that come into play in Spain were identified by the stakeholders interviewed:

- An understanding needs to come in place regarding how to valorise the digestate in Spain. Since each plant has a type of substrate with different compositions than the others, it is not clear now what can be considered or used as fertilizer because there are no regulations regarding this topic. This is creating an issue since very valuable digestate is being sold as lower quality material, losing its added value and losing the potential of recovering this residue from the digestion process.
- New regulations (after 2014, some listed in previous pages) have not really changed the landscape for biogas stakeholders interested in investing in biogas plants (e.g. technology providers that also invest in these plants, so they own a stake of it. Farmers normally do not have the financial means to invest by themselves). The normative for the generation of other renewable energies is more developed, but biogas still needs work in this regard to boost adoption. For one of the stakeholders (technology provider), specifically in 2014, a change in regulations (favoritism of other RES over biogas caused lowering biogas retribution) negatively affected all of the biogas plants they had invested in, many going into bankruptcy, which of course negatively affected their business and their engagement with the biogas/biomethane market.
- Added to this, the lack of uniformity on the authorization process among autonomic communities makes diving into the possibility of investing in a plant a more difficult one. In Spain the figure of “biogas project promotor” is an expert (usually with connections within the city town hall and other relevant government bodies) that helps you navigate all the bureaucracy surrounding the process (usually also interested in investing in the plant). Without this figure, the task would be very difficult, and it would take, at least, double the time. With an experienced promotor, the minimum time is around 2 years to obtain all the authorizations required.
- Among autonomic communities, also communication for transportation of manure and connections to the electric/natural gas grid are very heterogenous. Depending on the region of Spain, plants/farmers could be well communicated if there was a high concentration of farms there, but there are other regions that are more remote in all senses.
- Another aspect is that the upgrade of biogas to biomethane process is better regulated than the actual process to obtain biogas, so of course this could be an important bottle neck affecting the value-chain.

5.2.4 Policy priorities

Among the policy priorities identified via the interviews:

- Homogenization of the authorization process.
- Valorisation of digestate as fertilizer to boost its commercialization and use.
- Incentives and training for farmers so they feel more involved and have the tools necessary to show interest in biogas technologies.

5.3 Socioeconomic aspects

5.3.1 *Economic aspects*

- By training farmers and making them more familiar with biogas/biomethane and its benefits, the need for financing will probably increase. However, at the moment, public and private entities are interested in investing in biogas, but are moving slowly waiting for the regulatory/legislative conditions to improve. Biogas project promoters are a must if an investor wants to move forward with the implementation of a plant, they will normally form societies involving investors, a project promotor, and farmers in order to move the project forward.
- A very popular livestock farming business model in the country, especially for pig farming, is that very big food companies use the “integration model.” This somehow changes the role of the “farmer,” in the way that they somehow rent their space to these big companies to farm pigs and poultry. The farmer takes basic care of the animals and other services (like electricity), but the companies bring their own food and veterinarians to grow the animals. For this, the farmer receives payment for each grown pig/chicken, and these animals, of course, produce manure. The challenge is that this manure is left untreated and is not managed by the food company, so the farmer is the one left with the waste, and they are currently disposing it within their means. This has had a huge impact nationally, acting as huge contaminants.

5.3.2 *Social aspects*

- A potential explanation to these limitations in regulations is that the biogas topic is currently treated only as a RES topic, and not as an Agriculture and Livestock Farming topic; this makes it harder for the agricultural sector to feel involved in these matters.
- It is important to provide information to the neighbours of the plant to help demystify bad opinions that biogas is harmful to the environment.
- Farmers have very little context and information on the benefits of biogas technologies; however, they understand the challenges they are experiencing, but since biogas is so far from their core business, they lack that technical expertise to objectively look at the available solutions. To ease this, they should at least manage the essential information to help them understand why they should move their manure to a biogas plant, instead of dumping it on a field. This would entail training and convincing on why dropping their waste on a field is harmful for the environment, and also how they can get more implicated, how much will it cost and, of course, what benefits it will bring for them.

5.4 Stakeholders' priorities

The farmers' association and technology providers showed to have a high commitment with environmental safety and the transformation of Spain towards models like Germany, France, and Denmark, which are the referents regarding biogas technology and regulatory development.

Their current priorities lay on the standardization of practices within the country, the implementation of more detailed regulatory and legislative measures to define and promote the implementation of biogas/biomethane plants as well as the valorisation of digestate, along with the growth of electric and natural gas grids is also needed to ensure the successful uptake of RES.

The market has currently a relative level of maturity, especially for small plants (of around the 100 KWe), because these projects are much simpler to execute since they require less coordination with less manure providers. The bigger the plant, the higher the amount of manure needed, and in

the country, it is fairly complicated to identify and manage a large number of farmers that want to participate.

Regarding livestock farmers, they reported their farms to be almost 100% man ran, with almost all the workers being family members. These cattle farmers specified that they were not considering implementing a biogas plant and/or other biogas practices, and that they did not know much about the topic, confirming the challenges identified by the other interviewed stakeholders.

5.5 Overall assessment

In general, the gender balance in the livestock farming industry is with no doubt tilted towards male representation. There is no evidence of incentives specific for women in agriculture, nor of any other means to promote their participation in the sector.

The market is still young when compared to other EU-27 countries, and the highest maturity is being reached in the implementation of small plants, mostly plug-and-play models. The lack of support from legislations and regulations, the small amount of biomethane plants in comparison with biogas plants, the difficulty to connect to the grid, and also the long periods of authorization times and difficulty of the process itself are factors that are hindering the adoption of biogas and biomethane in Spain.

The information gathered through the answers given by interviewed stakeholders (technology providers, biogas association, and livestock farmers) were very much in line with the challenges identified through the initial desk research. All stakeholders agreed in most points regarding main challenges and the biogas potential of Spain.

The country currently has a huge biogas potential, but the adoption of these technologies will depend on the relevance the regulations and legislations give to its development, as well as to the fact that tools to boost their market uptake are made broadly available. There is a big gap identified with the farmers and the knowledge they need in order to consider participating in the biogas value-chain somehow (as manure providers, or as investors), since at the moment they do not seem to have the tools at their disposal to truly understand how biogas could solve the imminent problem of animal waste produced by the livestock farming sector. Of course, incentives also play an important factor, which could impact very positively on the way they perceive these new solutions.

Country: ITALY

5.6 State of Biogas and Biomethane in Livestock Farming

To comply with European Green Deal and Fit for 55 package, aiming at reducing 55% of emissions by 2030 and at reaching climate neutrality by 2050, Italy is developing and implementing new and sustainable energy sources with the goal to reduce the energy price and to reach, in the long run, decarbonization.

Among the renewable energy sources that in recent years have undergone strong growth, there is biogas. The eponymous sector soon became crucial, leading the country to rank fourth in the world after Germany, China and the United States.

It is interesting to point out that Italy has been developing its biogas sector since the early 90s, and actually introduced its first official subsidy, a green certificate system, in 1999. Most Italy's biogas plants were built after the introduction of the "all inclusive" FIT for small renewable energy plants (the *tariffa omnicomprensiva*) in 2008. Moreover, a sharp increase in the number of biogas plants in Italy happened between 2008 and 2012. As of January 2013, the Italian biogas support scheme changed and was considered less profitable by investors. Subsidies decreased relatively to the previous support framework, but were extended from 15 to 20 years. Nevertheless, both the number of biogas plants in Italy and the country biogas production continued to grow at a steady pace between 2013 and 2021 (Figure 15) (EBA statistical report, 2022)⁵⁸.

Figure 15: Development of biogas production (GWh) (left), and development of the number of biogas plants (right) (EBA Statistical Report 2022)⁵⁸

⁵⁸ European Biogas Association, 2022, Statistical Report Tracking biogas and biomethane deployment across Europe 2022, https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/_trashed-3/

Despite such a strong growth of biogas in Italy, its production is not homogenous among the various parts of the country: the distribution of biogas plants on the national territory confirms the gap between North and South of Italy.

According to GSE data, around 83.4% of the total national production of electricity from biogas is supplied by the regions of Northern Italy, where the main producer is Lombardy, that concentrates 34.6% of the national production, followed by Veneto (15.3%), Emilia Romagna (14.6%) and Piedmont (12.6%) (GSE, 2020)⁵⁹.

In order to concretely highlight the aspects at national and local level, a sample has been identified. The latter represents actors, directly and indirectly, involved in the implementation of biogas plants.

In particular, the following stakeholders have been identified and interviewed in order to better understand the state-of-the-art of biogas in Italy; among them: livestock farmers; financial institutions; public officers responsible for the plant authorization and technology provider.

Figure 16 Regional distribution of electricity production from biogas (GSE 2021)⁵⁹

5.7 Legal and Policy Framework

The regulation of the production of energy from renewables in Italy is governed by the Decree DM 06/07/2012⁶⁰ that entered into force definitively on 11 July 2012.

Moreover, the decree implemented the principles and general purposes that had been previously established by Legislative Decree 3 March 2011, n. 28 (legislative decree n. 28/2011), which in turn executed the European Directive on the promotion of renewable sources.

The aforementioned principles, established by the Legislative Decree, promoted the production of energy from renewables of natural sources and energy efficiency to an extent adequate to achieve the share of energy from renewable sources.

The decree 28/2011 has established the principle that the incentive criteria and incentive tools should tend to promote effectiveness, efficiency, simplification, and stability incentive systems over time, as well as the reduction of charges, a burden of consumers.

In detail, the Legislative Decree n. 28/2011 for the biogas was aimed at promoting:

⁵⁹ Rapporto Statistico GSE – FER 2020, https://www.gse.it/documenti_site/Documenti%20GSE/Rapporti%20statistici/Rapporto%20Statistico%20GSE%20-%20FER%202020.pdf

⁶⁰ Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico, 2012, DM 06/07/2012 https://www.gse.it/documenti_site/Documenti%20GSE/Servizi%20per%20te/FER%20ELETTRICHE/NORMATIVE/DM_6_LUGLIO_2012.pdf

- Efficient use of waste and by-products, zootechnical manure or by-products of agricultural, agro-food, agro-industrial, breeding activities e-forestry, of products obtained from dedicated non-food crops, as well as from short supply chains, framework contracts and supply chain agreements;
- The construction of plants operating in cogeneration;
- The construction and operation of plants by agricultural entrepreneurs fuelled by biomass and biogas used for agricultural activities, in particular micro and mini-generation.

5.7.1 Authorization Process for Instalment of Biogas System and Authorization for Injection in the Grid

The aforementioned Decree 28 of 3/03/2011 has introduced measures to simplify and streamline all the administrative procedures for the construction of renewable energy plants, both for the production of electricity and for the production of thermal energy. In particular, to realise and implement plants, four steps are required:

- 1) **Single Authorization (AU):** the AU is the tool that entitles one to build and make operational the plant and, where necessary, becomes a variant to the urban tool. Moreover, it has a maximum duration of 90 days net of the time allowed for the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) procedure, where necessary. The competence for the issue of the Single Authorization is in the hands of the Regions or Provinces delegated by them;
- 2) **Simplified Procedure Enabler (PAS):** The PAS has to be submitted to the Municipality at least 30 days before the starting of the works. It should be accompanied by a detailed report, signed by a qualified designer certifying the compatibility of the project with urban planning and building regulations in force. Moreover, it should be in compliance with safety and hygiene standards. If there won't be feedback or notifications 30 days after the presentation of the PAS, the plant realization can begin;
- 3) **Communication to the Municipality:** is the fulfilment provided to simplify the authorization process of some types of small plants for the production of electricity, heat and cold from RES, similar to free building activity. The initial communication of work should be accompanied by a detailed report signed by a qualified designer. It is not necessary to wait 30 days before starting work;
- 4) **Declaration/Communication of work:** the communication of work should be done through a notice of commencement of work (DILA). The DILA notice should be used even for all the modifications related to the existing installations or modifications to authorised projects which, without increasing the area occupied by the installations and related works and irrespective of the electrical power resulting from the intervention.

The authorization to connect the plant to the grid must be requested from the gas/electric power distributor, which indicate the exact place for the connection and its technical characteristics according with the technical rules set out by the relevant authority ([ARERA](#)).

The authorization to connect to the grid is Regarding instead the 'costs of connection to the national natural gas network they are mainly charged to the biomethane producers, those costs are calculated both according to the distance of the biomethane production plant to the natural gas network and according to the delivery pressure. Furthermore, the producers must install a

biomethane quality control system at their own expense, while the grid operators provide, if necessary, for the odorization of biomethane (REGATRACE, 2021)⁶¹.

5.7.2 Incentives Schemes

The incentives provided for the implementation of biogas plants are governed by the Ministerial Decree 23 June 2016 and its subsequent amendments. According to the Ministry of Enterprises and Made in Italy, the decree regulates the incentive of renewable sources other than photovoltaic.

The incentive period will last twenty years. Moreover, the new incentives are provided in compliance with the overall ceiling of 5.8 billion euros per year for renewable energy (except for photovoltaic).

Incentives are allocated through technology-differentiated downward auction procedures for large plants (>5 MW), while plants below this threshold will have to apply for registration in appropriate registers. However, the draft decree has been approved in advance by the European Commission to ensure its compatibility with the guidelines on State aid in the field of energy and the environment.

Further developments have taken place: **the Simplifications Degree 2020** has therefore introduced a partial derogation, allowing plants that have benefited from incentives to access the new auction or register procedures, with a 3% tariff reduction. This standard has been further strengthened by the Decree that implemented the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) (DL 7/11/2021).

Another step forward has been made with the **DL. 05 December 2013 (the Biomethane Decree)**. It clearly states the possibility to upgrade the biogas into biomethane, and inject it in the existing natural gas grid; it also defines the general framework for the biomethane production incentives and introduce the concept of **extended gas grid**: the union of gas transport grid, gas distribution grid, filling stations and systems for on road gas transport (i.e. tank trucks).

To be effective and allow the actual realisation of plants, the legal framework had to be complemented with technical rules on the gas quality, measurement procedures and systems, compression and injection equipment, grid standards etc that were published in the following years by the Authority for Energy and Gas Systems (AEEG, now [ARERA](#)); the whole process took a few years and ended in 2016 giving the possibility to connect plants while incentivising 3 different uses of the gas:

- Biomethane injected in the distribution grid of natural gas;
- Biomethane used in transport after injection into the natural gas grid;
- Biogas plants used in CAR (High efficiency cogeneration – “Cogenerazione ad Alto Rendimento”).

Less than two years later the DM 2 March 2018 clearly directed the choice of new plants toward the production of biomethane for the transport sector.

The biomethane production is promoted with the allocation of certificates of release for consumption ("Certificati di Immissione in Consumo di biocarburanti", better known as "CIC") to be provided to those subjects who release non-renewable fuels for consumption (REGATRACE, 2021)⁶¹. A CIC is assigned every 5 GCal if the biomethane is produced with manure and agricultural

⁶¹ REGATRACE, 2021, Renewable Gas Trade Centre, D6.1 Mapping the state of play of renewable gases in Europe <https://www.regatrace.eu/>

residues (complete list specified in Decree of 10 October 2014). The methane produced with these substrates is considered an 'advanced' biofuel and can be sold at a fixed and advantageous price to the [GSE](#) Gestore Servizi Energetici (Energy Service Manager) that also withdraws the CIC assigning them a value of 375€ each.

5.7.3 *Related legal aspects and policy priorities*

Policy priorities

Among the policy priorities there is the need to support all the actors in all the steps of the energy transition process.

In particular, an increase of awareness on the importance of implementing new energy sources, among them the biogas, will be crucial. On this point, effective raising awareness campaigns, aimed at all the various actors involved in the sector, should be created with the goal to underline how biogas, e.g., could be exploited as a dispatchable source to cover the production gaps of the other RES.

Biogas is one of the most interesting renewable energies because, together with the hydroelectric one, is the only fully dispatchable source. This means that, unlike the others, the production can be scheduled for example during the night or to meet the consumption peaks; in principle, these plants can also act as a buffer for the electric grid and/or be the link between the electric and gas grid (power to gas). This kind of services would be very useful to manage the network and increase the renewable energy share, but a regulatory framework and new incentive schemes are required.

Related legal aspects

Renewable Energy Communities

The European directives RED II (renewable energy directive) and EMD (recast electricity market directive) introducing the concepts of 'citizen energy communities' (CEC) and 'Renewable Energy Communities' (CER) were transposed in Italy with Legislative Decree 199/2021, which came into force on 24/01/2022 allowing the creation of these new kinds of organizations where citizens can share energy on a peer-to-peer basis. A CHP biogas plant can be an excellent solution to provide the base load for the energy requirements of the community.

Maximum nitrogen content

The two decrees D.Leg.152 11/05/1999 and the DM 07/04/2006⁶² introduced two important restrictions:

- The definition and identification of the Vulnerable Areas to Nitrates (ZVN) where it is not possible to spread livestock effluents that exceed 170 kg/(hectar*year) of nitrogen. This limitation applies to digestate too;
- The introduction of agricultural Action Plans that define how and when livestock manure, or digestate, can be spread in the fields. Thus, it is important to consider the need to manage the digestate when preparing a business plan for the realization of a biogas plant: it can require large reservoirs to store it and hundreds of hectares leading to unexpected costs.

⁶² Ministero delle Politiche Agricole e Forestali, Gazzetta ufficiale N109 12/05/2006 <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2006/05/12/06A04328/sq>

International biomethane market. Currently it doesn't exist a European market for biomethane and it is not possible to import biomethane. In the long term, the creation of an EU regulation or the sign of bilateral agreements between States can boost the market.

5.8 Socio-economic Framework

5.8.1 Economic Aspects

One of the most important economic aspects to underline is the difficulty to invest in this period characterised by variable rates; investments that are slowed down by the very long and complex authorised processes for most of the farmers. Moreover, new biogas plants authorization procedures have seen a sharp slowdown due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

5.8.2 Social Aspects

The implementation of biogas plants represents a great advantage where biogas it is not only a new source of renewable energy, but it should also be seen as a crucial element of the farm: it allows to diversify revenues, to produce energy, to manage the flows of sewage and agricultural residues and to have soil improvers / fertilisers.

However, in the biogas implementation various barriers arise even at social level and among the social aspects the following should be underlined:

- Difficulties in developing cooperative or biogas community plants;
- Opposition dynamics (NIMBY) that slow the implementation of new biogas plants;
- Biogas as alien theme: to date, most of the farmers do not have a proper knowledge of the importance of developing and implementing new renewable energy sources as biogas;
- There are no clear guidelines accessible to everyone for the implementation of new plants.

5.9 Overall Assessment

In general, in recent years the biogas sector at national level is growing despite the various social, political, and economic difficulties that the various stakeholders encounter.

The great chance to make this further qualitative leap comes today from the Recovery Fund. The latter can help the development of biogas plants at national level, helping farmers to reduce their energy expenditures.

The importance of continuing to invest in biogas will be crucial for Italy, leading even the country to respect the European Commission objectives and the achievement of climate neutrality.

6. Country: Denmark

6.1 State of biogas and biomethane in livestock farming

Denmark has a livestock density among the highest in the world. This, combined with being surrounded by vulnerable nature such as the Baltic Sea, has paved the way for a considerable effort in developing skills and innovative technologies for handling of livestock manure in an environmentally safe way. The growing awareness of resource depletion and climate challenges has further clarified the huge potential for reducing greenhouse gas emissions from livestock production by utilising the energy content and fertiliser value of manure. A large number of Danish pig and dairy farmers are involved in livestock manure-based biogas production, most of them via farmer cooperative owned industrial size biogas plants.

The biogas production in Denmark has increased rapidly since 2012, and more than 30% of the gas in the gas grid was renewable biomethane in 2022. More than 11 million tons of biomass are used to produce biogas and fertiliser on an annual basis.

Figure 17: Existing biogas plants and the expected biomethane production for the gas grid in Denmark. Map from the Danish Energy Agency's homepage (DEAh, 2023)⁶³

Figure 18: Recent and expected biogas use in Denmark (Støckler, 2020)⁶⁴

⁶³ Danish Energy Agency homepage, 2023, <https://ens.dk/ansvarsomraader/bioenergi/produktion-af-biogas>

⁶⁴ Michael Støckler mm., Food and Bio Cluster Denmark, 2020, Biogas production, Insights and experiences from the Danish Biogas Sector.

The biogas produced in Denmark is used for heating, transport, industrial processes, and is upgraded to the gas network and for electricity production.

Figure 19: The expected development in production of renewable gas in Denmark (Biogas, 2022)⁶⁵.

It is expected that, by 2035, the Danish biogas production will represent almost 100% of the gas used (Figure 19). Natural gas is being phased out and the pace at which it happens is expected to be increased due to the ongoing war in Ukraine.

Figure 20: Expected development in biogas production split into: Industrial waste, source-sorted organic waste, energy crops, manure, deep bedding, crop residues, straw; Danish Energy Agency (Jürgens, 2021)⁶⁶.

The Danish Energy Agency has made a projection of the expected biogas production in Denmark (Figure 20). Biogas production must be based on industrial waste, source-separated household waste, energy crops, slurry, deep bedding, crop residues and straw.

Figure 21: Expected development in biogas production split into: Industrial waste, source-sorted organic waste, energy crops, manure, deep bedding, crop residues, straw; by Biogas Danmark (Jürgens, 2021)⁶⁶.

⁶⁵ Biogas Danmark, 2022, Biogas Outlook 2022, Production and use of biogas in Denmark 2021-2035.

⁶⁶ Jonas Jürgens, Danish Energy Agency and Claus Mortensen, Food and Bio Cluster Denmark, 2021, Biogas policy in Denmark – An overview of technology and supportive reports from 2013-2021.

Biogas Danmark, the national trade organisation for everyone with an interest in biogas, has made a corresponding projection of the expected development in biogas production and they believe that the expansion can be faster and more extensive (Figure 21).

Figure 22: The distribution of the total amount of livestock manure in Denmark, data provided by ConTerra.

Figure 23: The share of livestock manure delivered to biogas production in Denmark in 2021. In some areas more than 50% of livestock manure is used for biogas production. Figure provided by (ConTerra, 2022)⁶⁷

There is a great deal of overlap between the density of livestock production and the part of livestock manure that is used for biogas production.

Since 2021, the share of livestock manure used for biogas production has increased considerably.

⁶⁷ ConTerra, 2022, Figures on the use of livestock manure for biogas production, <http://www.conterra.dk/>

6.2 Legal and policy framework

National policies have promoted the development of solutions for handling of manure. Initially to reduce its harmful environmental impacts, and now to exploit its potential for climate friendly energy.

Livestock manure has always been considered an important resource in Denmark. Agriculture plays a significant role in Denmark's economy and is characterised by large volumes of livestock production that, for instance, makes Denmark the world's number one exporter of pork. The quantity of livestock manure being produced in Denmark is about 35 million tons per year.

Environmental policies

Until the early 1980's, livestock manure was just considered a natural crop fertiliser that, along with high crop productivity needs and low energy prices, lost ground to mineral fertilisers. However, in 1985 to reduce problems with nutrient leaching and water quality the Government launched the so-called NPO (nitrogen and phosphorus) plan that set requirements to create harmony between the farmed area and the number of livestock, as well as to the minimum capacity for storage of manure on farms. Still tighter regulations from both the EU and the Danish government have since then triggered a technological development that has resulted in huge amounts of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) in livestock manure today being utilised with almost the same efficiency as that of mineral fertilisers, alleviating the environment from N and P loads, and farmers from the costs of purchasing fertilisers.

Today, the environmental considerations go even further: it is not only a question of saving the environment from pollution, but also a question of resource efficiency and use of local resources.

Climate policies

The recognition of global warming and its harmful effects, in Denmark as well as internationally, led to the introduction of policy measures to reduce its impacts. The United Nations' Kyoto Protocol committed Denmark to a CO₂ reduction since 2005.

Bio-security aspects

EU's hygiene package from 2003 determines that safety of food depends on all steps in the supply chain from field to fork, i.e. that every farm is part of the food supply chain. Food safety deals with contamination of food with microbes, plastic, chemicals and foreign bodies. For livestock farms, ensuring a high food quality is focused on dealing with the prevention of contamination of products such as milk contaminated with livestock manure. In Denmark, a Hygiene Business Code (national guidelines) was developed in cooperation between farmers' organizations and the veterinary and other authorities. Additionally, a number of private quality certification schemes have been established. The focus on food safety and hygiene has increased the requirements to manure handling and processing technologies, so that it does not leak and is easy to clean.

6.2.1 *Autorization process for instalment of biogas systems*

Permits needed will depend, among other things, on the size of the facility. For larger installations, the following must be sought as a minimum:

- Local plan
- Municipal plan supplement
- VVM permit
- Environmental approval and impact report
- Application for wastewater conditions

- Application for wired livestock manure
- Building permit

For the very large plants, they must also be approved in accordance with the risk order, this depends on the amount of gas that can be stored at the plant.

For smaller farm facilities, the local plan and municipal plan supplement can be omitted.

In addition, in other departments, it must be documented how the degassed biomass is disposed of as fertiliser and that it is in accordance with the fertiliser regulations.

6.2.2 *Incentives schemes*

Market drivers for biogas in Denmark:

- Dedicated governmental support schemes
- Investment support
- Feed-in tariffs
- Restricted application of nitrogen and phosphorous on fields
- Ban on organic waste on landfill (1998)
- National target of minimum 50% recycling of household solid waste by 2023
- Fees for waste treatment => Co-digestion
- Follow-up programs on technical challenges
- Biogas allowed in the natural gas network
- Blending obligation for RE-transportation fuels (5,75–10%)

The Danish biogas technology has been developing for 30 years supported by different incentives and subsidy schemes. The former subsidy scheme, launched in 2012, has accelerated the development and increased the production of biogas and the amount of renewable natural gas in the natural gas grid.

Biogas production links energy production to the treatment of manure and organic waste. In Denmark, manure and organic waste from industry, service-sector and households are usually co-digested in agricultural biogas plants.

To be eligible for subsidies, biogas production cannot exceed 5% energy crops in the input feedstocks. The subsidies are given to the user of the biogas for the different purposes. This includes users of biogas for Renewable Natural Gas (RNG) production. Previously, an investment support scheme existed for biogas plants, but it was terminated in 2016.

6.2.3 *Governmental support schemes*

The following uses of biogas receive support as stated in the table below:

- Production of electricity
- Upgraded biogas feed in the natural gas grid or cleaned biogas delivered to a town gas grid
- Use of biogas for process purposes in the industry
- Use of biogas as a transport fuel
- Use of biogas for heating purposes

Table 7: Subsidies scheme in Denmark for the use of Biogas in US dollars.

Biogas subsidy scheme in Denmark from 2012	General subsidy	Bonus regulated in relation to the natural gas price	Bonus, that is phased out in 2020	Total subsidy
	USD/GJ	USD/GJ	USD/GJ	USD/GJ
Upgrading	12,14	3,99	1,54	17,67
Process	5,99	3,99	1,54	11,52
Transport	5,99	3,99	1,54	11,52
Heat	0,00	3,99	1,54	5,53
	USD/kWh	USD/kWh	USD/kWh	USD/kWh
Electricity				
Fixed price incl electricity price	0,122	0,040	0,015	0,177
Fixed Premium on top of electricity price	0,066	0,040	0,015	0,122

6.2.4 The Danish market model for trade of renewable natural gas

The producers that decide not to use the biogas on their own, can sell it on the market for renewable natural gas that can roughly be said to consist of the following three elements:

- Market: Trading of the energy in the conventional gas market.
- Grid: The physical transportation of the renewable natural gas in the gas grid.
- Green Value: Virtual trading of the “green” value of the renewable natural gas.

Trading and transportation of the biogas in the conventional gas market

In order to trade biogas in the conventional gas market, the biogas producer or owner of the biogas upgrade facility must enter into an agreement with a biogas seller – or decide to register as a biogas seller at The Danish Gas Transmission Operator, Energinet.

Furthermore, it is also required that the biogas seller either enters into an agreement with a so-called shipper or registers as one. This is because the shippers are responsible for transporting the biogas to the gas market and in the grid.

When the biogas is injected and nominated into the commercial flow of the gas market, it is no longer possible to differentiate between the conventional flow of fossil-based natural gas and the renewable natural gas. This means that as soon as the biogas enters the gas grid, thus the commercial flow of the gas market, it is considered natural gas and will be traded on the same terms as conventional natural gas, thus also priced accordingly.

Virtual trading of the “green” value of the biogas

As mentioned, it is not possible to distinguish the biogas from the other gas when it is injected into the gas grid. In order to do so, various virtual trading schemes have been set up based on market requirements and demand.

Guarantees of Origin

In Denmark and some other European countries national Guarantees of Origin (GO) registries have voluntarily been established with the purpose of documenting the renewable attributes of the biogas supplied to the gas grid. Hence the GO scheme’s function is to verify that the energy originates from renewable sources and the purchased quantity only is sold once preventing double counting.

GO are considered as a market-based instrument which can be used by private households or companies who voluntarily choose to have part, or all of their gas consumption covered by renewable sources. Voluntary purchases of GOs have mainly been done by companies in connection with their CSR-strategies, and, to a lesser extent, private households. Recently,

municipalities have also started buying GOs in relation to the implementation of gas-driven busses for public transportation.

6.2.5 Policy priorities

In Denmark, there is a major political focus on the expansion and use of biogas. Biogas is seen as an opportunity to balance renewable energy production, which is supplied from solar cells and wind turbines. By expanding biogas production and upgrading the gas and distributing it via the gas network, you can establish a storage function that is not possible to establish in connection with solar and wind. Denmark has some very large storage facilities for gas, and these can be used both to balance energy consumption for heat and industrial processes, and it can also be used to balance electricity production.

There is a very large political focus on developing Power2X technologies in Denmark, and here biogas production can also play a decisive role. Many of the products that are possible to produce using electrolysis and Power2x are dependent on a carbon source, and here carbon dioxide production in connection with biogas is an obvious possibility. Biogas typically consists of 35-40% CO₂ and when the biogas is upgraded, this is separated from the biomethane and is found in a concentrated form. CO₂ from the biogas plants is therefore an obvious resource in connection with the production of methanol, jet fuel, plastic and various other industrial products.

It has been a political priority in Denmark for many years to optimize the use of livestock manure (manure and deep litter) for fertilizer purposes, and this has resulted in more than 2/3 of all fertilisers used in Denmark originating from livestock production. The biogas plants help to optimize this utilization by improving the quality and distribution of the nutrients.

6.3 Socioeconomic aspects

6.3.1 Economic aspects

The Danish support incentives are described earlier. A very successful scheme for the production of biogas was introduced in Denmark in 2012. At the same time, it became possible to distribute upgraded biogas via the national gas network. Overall, this means a very strong expansion of Danish biogas production, and in 2022 biogas made up more than 30% of the total amount of gas used in Denmark.

A new support system is expected to be implemented from 2024 until 2030, in which support for production will run for 20 years from the first-time support is paid under the scheme. There is an ongoing negotiation about how much support should be offered and how quickly it should be implemented.

6.3.2 Social aspects

Denmark is a relatively small country with a population slightly less than 6 million and in relation to its size, Denmark has a very large animal production.

Table 8: Employed in agriculture and horticulture by type and time. From (Statistics Denmark, 2021)⁶⁸

The whole country, Denmark			
Number of people		Year	
		2018	2020
	Personal users	31.725	30.118
	Manager	2.389	3.030
	Working spouse	10.538	9.855
	Family helper	7.710	4.339
	Permanent foreign help	27.439	26.429
	Aassistance in total	35.149	30.768
	Employed in total	79.801	73.771

⁶⁸ Statistics Denmark, 2021, <https://www.statbank.dk/FOLK1A>

According to the tables, only a small part of the Danish population is employed in agriculture, overall it is around 1 percent, as a significant part of the workforce are foreigners who help on the farms.

Table 9: Number of farms by farm type and time. From (Statistics Denmark, 2021)⁶⁸⁶⁸

The whole country, Denmark				
Agricultural enterprises		Year	2020	2021
	Farms with dairy cattle		2.470	2.369
	Farms with cattle breeding and fattening		3.841	3.486
	Farms with rough foraging livestock in general		3.310	3.334
	Pig farms		2.039	1.909
	Farms with poultry		292	277

The number of farms with livestock production in Denmark has been declining for many years. On the other hand, production has not fallen, which is due to the fact that the individual farms are getting bigger and bigger.

6.4 Overall assessment

The conditions for the production of biogas in Denmark are very favourable. There have been several support schemes that have helped to promote biogas production. In particular, an energy agreement from 2012 and the possibility to upgrade biogas and sell it via the national gas network have boosted Danish biogas production tremendously. Biogas production takes place both at water treatment facilities, at industrial plants and at agricultural-based plants. Most of the expansion has taken place at the agricultural-based facilities and some of these are now very large and process 0.5-1 million tons of biomass per year.

The agricultural-based biogas plants are placed as a starting point in the geographical areas where there is a large livestock production. Livestock manure is the basic substrate, but it is necessary to add other biomass with a higher energy content to increase biogas production. The gas potential in manure slurry is low and it is difficult to run plants economically if other biomass cannot be added such as residual flows from industry, household waste or residual products from agriculture including straw etc.

In certain areas of Denmark, more than 50% of livestock manure is already used for biogas production.

There is a great political desire and will to promote biogas production, and it is the expectation that 100% of the gas used in Denmark must come from renewable sources, with biogas as the dominant contributor.

Biogas production is not only seen as a production of energy in the form of the gas that is used for heat, power, cogeneration, industry and transport, but is also an environmental initiative that can contribute to limiting emissions from livestock production and help to optimize the utilization of livestock manure for fertiliser. Biogas production is an excellent technology that contributes to solving several different challenges in the Danish society.

7. Country: Slovakia

The Slovak Republic spreads over an area of 49,036 km² of which around 48% is agricultural land and 40% is covered by forests. The agricultural land is composed of around 71 % arable soils and 28% permanent grassland, The structure of arable land utilisation is shown Figure 24⁶⁹.

Animal breeding is an important sector of the Slovak economy. Its share in the gross agricultural production is more than 60%. The natural conditions of Slovakia lead to breed-varied animal production as shown in Figure 25 and further elaborated in the next chapter regarding the biogas potential.

The overview of the central livestock register (September 2022) states 56418 active farms in Slovakia, out of which 45196 are livestock farms⁷⁰.

Slovakian agriculture is characterized by a dual farm structure, with a high proportion (80%) of small farms with small herds (up to EUR 15,000 of standard output), and a small number of large farms (1,180) with significant number of animals and standard output higher than EUR 250,000. This is mainly true of beef cattle, when almost 85% of milk cows are bred on farms with a concentration of 50 and more heads. A similar situation holds in the case of pigs, and about 35% of the sheep population is owned by individual farmers. Factory farming, mainly of milk cows, has experienced significant modernisation during the last 10 years and, nowadays, almost 60% of cows are bred in free stalls with milking in modern milk houses⁷¹.

Despite these facts, agriculture in Slovakia contributes (according to statistics from 2021) only 1.74% to the growth domestic product (GDP) compares to services (59.14%) and industry (28.19%)⁷².

Labour productivity in agriculture and in the food industry is very low, respectively 46% and 39% of the EU average. The continuous decrease of employees in agriculture ranks Slovakia among the countries with the lowest share of agricultural workers from total employees (half the EU

Figure 24. Structure of arable land utilization

Figure 25. Livestock as of December 2022 in Slovakia

⁶⁹ Statistic Office of the Slovak Republic: [Slovak Republic in figures 2022](#).

⁷⁰ <https://www.pssr.sk/wp-content/uploads/cehz/subory/archiv/cehz0922.pdf>

⁷¹ Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic: <https://www.mpsr.sk/en/index.php?navID=26>

⁷² www.statista.com: [Slovakia: Distribution of gross domestic product \(GDP\) across economic sectors from 2011 to 2021](#)

average).⁷³ At the EU level, around 30% of agricultural farms are operated by women - one farm in five, and in rural areas of the EU women represent over 50% of the rural population. In Slovakia, only 19.18% of farms are operated by female⁷⁴, but the percentage of women working in agriculture is higher.

7.1 State of biogas and biomethane in livestock farming

Over the last 20 years, there has been the significant development in the production of energy from biogas Slovakia. Figure 26 in the right and Table 10 below show the energy mix for the energy production in Slovakia for 2021 based upon the data from Short-term electricity Market Operator (hereinafter referred to as OKTE)⁷⁵.

In total, biomass energy accounted for 1.18TWh and represented 4.27% of the total production.

Estimation of the biogas/biomethane potential & trends: according to the statistics of Slovak Biogas Association, the total potential for biogas production from animal excrement in Slovakia is approximately 409 million m³. If added to this amount the potential calculated⁷⁶ for the biogas from maize silage, we will have a sum of 528 to 840 mil. m³/year.

Figure 26. Energy mix in Slovakia (April 2022, OKTE)

Table 10. Energy Production Mix, Slovakia, 2021⁷⁷

2021	RE unspecified	RE biomass	RE solar	RE geothermal	RE wind	RE hydro	Nuclear	FO unspecified	FO hard coal	FO lignite	FO oil	FO gas	Total
%	0.34%	4.27%	2.21%	0	0.02%	15.4%	52.88%	4.4%	1.13%	2.79%	1.16%	15.4%	100%
TWh	0.09	1.18	0.62	0	0.01	4.27	14.66	1.22	0.31	0.77	0.32	4.27	27.73
TOT	22.24 % (6.17 TWh)						52.88% (14.66 TWh)	24.88% (6,90 TWh)					1005 (27.73 TWh)

Considering for each m³ of biogas 1.7 to 2.2 kWh of electricity and 2.2 to 4 kWh of heat (HorbaJ and Mikolaj)⁷⁸, from biogas obtained through animal excrement, we get 818 GWh of electricity and

⁷³ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-09/rdp-factsheet-slovakia_en.pdf

⁷⁴ [Bridging the Gender Gap in the Agricultural Sector: Evidence from European Union Countries](#)

⁷⁵ Short-term electricity Market Operator's data (OKTE): <https://www.okte.sk/en/guarantees-of-origin/statistics/national-energy-mix/> - Energy Production Mix 2021

⁷⁶ Slovak Biogas Association (<https://sba-sk.sk/>).

⁷⁷ Ditto

⁷⁸ HORBAJ, – MIKOLAJ, 2003. Zjednodušený výpočet množstva bioplynu vznikajúceho z exkrementov v poľnohospodárstve, grafické určenie návratnosti investície a vhodného typu kogeneračnej jednotky/ HORBAJ, - MIKOLAJ, 2003. Simplified calculation of the amount of biogas produced from excreta in agriculture, graphical determination of the return on investment and the appropriate type of cogeneration unit. In Biom.cz [online]. 2003. ISSN: 1801-2655. Available online: <https://biom.cz/cz/odborne-clanky/zjednoduseny-vypocet-mnozstva-bioplynu-vznikajuceho-z-exkrementov-v-polnohospodarstve-graficke-urceni-navratnosti>

1,636 GWh of heat. Biogas from maize silage represents 238 GWh of electricity and 476 GWh of heat. Considering all active biogas plants (hereinafter referred to as BGPs) producing by cogeneration, 126.8 million m³ of biomethane would have been produced. If taking into account only BGP, which could be connected to a high-pressure gas grid, it would be approximately 28 Mm³. Other BGPs could deliver to a medium-pressure gas grid (after approval of Slovak gas industry distribution, hereinafter referred to as SPP-D) or fill produced biomethane into tankers for customers.

The potential of biomethane production from available raw materials other than targeted crops theoretically represents 340.6 million m³ of biomethane. According to Gas for Climate estimates, the potential of Slovakia is 250 million m³ of biomethane from anaerobic fermentation and 500 million m³ from gasification (thermal gasification)⁷⁹.

Regarding biomethane production, Slovakia produced its first biomethane volumes in February 2022 (Jelšava plant). According to Slovak Biogas Association (hereinafter referred to as SBA) findings, 15 BGPs - out of 76 currently active (in 2022) - are considering conversion to biomethane.

Biogas is produced in Slovakia from various substrates including energy crops, excrement of farm animals, food and agricultural residues and kitchen residues.

For a better orientation in the options of input raw materials, next Table 11 with a statistical overview is presented. The table compares data for the year 2008, because the development of RES and BGP only started at the end of 2009, when the Act on RES 309/2009 came into force.

Table 11. Statistical overview of land, its use and livestock breeding^{80 81 82}

	2009	2021
Agricultural land (thousand ha)	2,373.6	
Used agricultural land (thousand ha)	1,856.1	
Arable land (thousand ha)	1,326.5	
Unused agricultural land (thousand ha)	529.6	
Permanent grasslands (thousand ha)	512.0	
Maize for grain (thousand ha)	148.8	203.4
Maize for green and silage (thousand ha)	81.8	66.2
Cattle (thousands)	488.4	418.2
Pigs (thousands)	748.5	432.8
Sheep and goats (thousands)	361.6	269.4
Poultry (thousand pcs)	11,228.1	10,364.5
Horses (thousands)	8.4	6.7

Table 11 shows a decrease in livestock numbers is evident, as well as in the cultivation of maize for silage. Thus, it is clear that the BGP did not create pressure for increased maize silage cultivation. According to Slovak Biogas Association (SBA) estimates, half of the maize for silage is

⁷⁹ <https://gasforclimate2050.eu/publications/>

⁸⁰ Úrad geodézie, kartografie a katastra SR/Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastre Authority of the Slovak Republic: <https://www.skgeodesy.sk/sk/ugkk/kataster-nehnutelnosti/sumarne-udaje-katastra-podnom-fonde/>

⁸¹ [Súpis plôch osiatych poľnohospodárskymi plodinami k 20.5.2021/](#) Inventory of areas sown with agricultural crops as of 20.5.2021: Statistics Office of the Slovak Republic

⁸² [Súpis hospodárskych zvierat k 31.12.2021/](#) Livestock inventory as at 31.12.2021: Statistics Office of the Slovak Republic

currently produced for BGP. If we were to consider the production of maize silage as the only input for all BGP, its area would be approximately 53,994 ha, which is only 3.8% of all arable land.

Considering the stabled animals, the total amount of manure produced and gas potential is calculated in Table 12. However, considering logistic barriers (e.g. manure transport), we can estimate that a maximum 70% of the potential can be exploited.

Biogas plants in Slovakia: The situation in Slovakia is a bit specific, because there are either the agricultural cooperatives as one entity together with the BGP (might be split, but the owners are usually the same), or the BGPs as separate entities that work closely with one or more agricultural cooperatives, or several farmers in the area. The BGPs operates on wet fermentation.

Table 12. Theoretical recalculation of manure and slurry production and biomethane production potential from stable livestock

	Together (Thousand pcs)	Excrement (Thousand ton/year)	Biomethane potential (Million m ³ /year)
Cattle	348.2	4,860	49.7
Pigs	432.8	590.7	6.0
Poultry	10,364.5	258	6.5
Sheep and goats	179.6	49	2.7
Cattle	348.2	4,860	49.7
Together	11,325.2	5,758.8	64.8

Since 2014, 109 biogas stations (BGP) were built in Slovakia with an average electrical output of 0.89 MW and a total capacity of 96.59 MWe. 32 BGP were built with a capacity of up to 0.9 MW, and the rest are in the range of 0.9-1 MW. One BGP has an installed capacity of 2.83 MW. The last BGP connected to the network was built in 2014, after this year due to the halt in the connection of RES to the distribution network, as well as a dramatic reduction in purchase prices that do not allow economic return, no new BGP were connected to the network.

Figure 27. Maps of biogas plants in Slovakia

In 2022, according to Short-term electricity Market Operator (hereinafter referred to as OKTE), only 76 BGP are fully active shown in Figure 27⁸³. In 2021, BGP supplied 507.5 GWh of electricity and produced 608.9 GWh of heat.

Due to inappropriately set state support, BGP are in a bad financial situation and currently 17 BGPs are already completely shut down. Another 16 BGPs are temporarily shut down or at minimum power and are deciding whether to continue operating.

The digestate, to be scattered over fields, has to be analysed and receive a permit for application the Central Agricultural Inspection and Testing Institute (ÚKSUP)⁸⁴ that issues permits with conditions under which the digestate can be used. No clear rules, no conditions issued by The

⁸³ https://sba-sk.sk/biopllynovne-stanice/?zdroj_typ%5B%5D=1&zdroj_typ%5B%5D=3&zdroj_typ%5B%5D=2

⁸⁴ <https://www.slov-lex.sk/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/2000/136/20220716>

Slovak Ministry of Agriculture and Regional Development exists. Therefore, there is always a preliminary caution of using digestate for fertilization, which might gradually limit the use of digestate to minimum, even to stop its production. In addition, it is impossible to export digestate. The BGPs operate on a continuous basis and their storage capacity for the emerging digestate is limited (determined by law for a minimum of 6 months of digestate production). If the storage capacities would be filled, it would be impossible to continue dosing the input raw materials. This would result in a decrease or a complete halt in biogas production.

The biogas and biomethane station need heat and power to run; they are usually provided by the cogeneration unit (CHP). In the case of conversion to BMP, it is necessary to replace the original CHP with a smaller one to provide power, to buy it from the grid or use another source.

Based upon a survey from May 2022 conducted by SBA, several suppliers are able to supply and install the technology for biomethane stations. In all cases, these are biomethane separation membrane systems. The cost of a necessary technology for the existing BGP potentially injecting biomethane into the gas network, with an hourly output of approx. 250 m³, is between € 1.7 - 2.5 million. This output approximately corresponds to the biomethane production of the current 1 MW BGP. This price includes membrane technology, compressor, chromatograph, flow measurement, odorization, propanization, compressor and network injection. The investment cost for a completely new BMP, even with the necessary technology, is approximately € 5 - 5.5 million. For BMPs that do not have a high-pressure gas pipeline (VTL) nearby, it is possible to compress (bio-CNG) or liquefy biomethane (bio-LNG). This modification costs approximately € 3.5 million, including the upgrade of biogas. Another cost is the connection from BMP to the VTL network, which is approximately 100,000 €/km. The estimated delivery time of the technology is approximately 8 - 10 months.

According to the interviewee, there is strong and developed market in this sector in Slovakia - there are enough companies engaged in the BGPs' construction and servicing. Currently due to the energy crisis there is a growing interest in BGPs in CHP and biomethane, but the large investment necessary is an important barrier to the technology wider diffusion.

To the main biogas/biomethane technology suppliers belong [agriKomp \(construction\)](#), [Hutira \(technology\)](#), [Elkoplast \(technology for processing biowaste\)](#), [Airproducts \(gas technology\)](#), _Energie; Enserv; MWK; Tomášek Servis (Gas Control, Bioproject); EnviTec etc.

There is only one biomethane station which gas istraded abroad; all the other plants are CHP. The heat is used in smaller villages, social facilities, agricultural buildings and greenhouses.

7.2 Legal and policy framework

The main findings regarding the legal and policy framework are the following:

- Law on energetics (Act.No.656/2004 Coll.) set the general framework and rules of energy market.
- Law on promotion of RES (ActNo.309/2009 Coll.) and production of electricity and heat - CHP
- National Action Plan for RES (NAP for RES 2010) specify the feed in tariffs policy and determine the rules for the redemption prices creation and regulation. The feed in tariffs is

annually issued by Price decision of Regulatory Office (RONI) what brings operators and potential investors into uncertainty in profitability and return of investments⁸⁵.

- Regulation of Regulatory Office for Network Industries (ÚRSO/RONI) No. 221/2013 Coll.86 – the slowdown in the positive development trend in the production of energy from biogas - grading the purchase price of electricity according to BGPs installed capacity into four groups (the higher installed capacity the lower price). The most used type, i.e., BGPs over 0.75 MW, thus fell into the lowest price category, which led to their unprofitability. In addition, a stop-state a general suspension of the acceptance of applications for the connection of electricity generation facilities to distribution systems with an output of more than 10 kW came into force in 2014. The stop-state was supposed to ensure the safety and stability of the power system. It was cancelled in April 2021, when new cross-border interconnections of the Slovak and Hungarian transmission systems were launched, making it possible to connect an additional installed capacity of 1,837 MW to the electricity system.
- In 2015, Act no. 79/2015 Coll. on waste, which obliges municipalities and catering operators, to separate biodegradable municipal waste. Together with the abolition of the stop-state to grid connection and potential support for renewable energy in accordance with the Recovery and Resilience Plan/RRP (€62 million should be invested in the modernization of biogas and small hydropower plants) this law can be an important step for the future of energy production from biogas. In addition, the conversion of waste into digestate itself would be an added value.
- The Decree of the Ministry of the Environment no.200/2018Coll., on the treatment of pollutants, on the emergency plan and the procedure for dealing with extraordinary water deterioration⁸⁷ (effective from 15/07/2018) - applies without exception to all BGPs, including the operating ones.

The constant changes in the legal framework brought uncertainty to development plans and suspended new projects. On the other hand, they sparked a discussion about the future of bioenergy in Slovakia. AEBIOM (EBA 2016) does not consider the production of bioenergy from silage to be long-term sustainable. It is recommended to focus on agriculture and animal husbandry, which have a significant amount of processable waste. The average installed capacity of such stations should be smaller – up to 250 kW. In addition, the final digestate is considered a valuable organic fertilizer. Larger biogas plants with an installed capacity of more than 1 MW appear to be an efficient solution for the production of biomethane or the combined production of heat and electricity.

7.2.1 Authorization process for instalment of biogas system

The authorization to instal the plant is issued by the Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic (MŽP SR). The timeframe for authorization will depend on the type and complexity of installation. Generally, it can take anywhere from three to six months to receive authorization. The overall process involves submitting an application to the MŽP SR with all necessary information and

⁸⁵https://www.researchgate.net/publication/314096691_The_role_of_energy_policy_in_agricultural_biogas_energy_production_in_Visegrad_countries

⁸⁶ The guarantee of mandatory electricity purchase by distribution companies with a fixed amount of purchase prices for a period of 15 years. (Author's note).

⁸⁷ <https://www.slov-lex.sk/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/2018/200/20180715>

documents regarding the project; including a project description, a list of materials and equipment to be used, information on safety and environmental protection. The authorization is then presented to the municipality and local authorities. Once all permits are in place, the biogas plant can be installed.

The effective possibility to connect a RES is a source of disappointment in Slovakia. Since 2013, the regional distribution companies have taken the same view that there is simply no capacity in the system to connect any new sources. Not even to local distribution systems (LDS). As a consequence, building a RES plant bigger than 10 kW in has been an almost impossible task since 2013. Success stories are more of an exception to the rule. The long-awaited (and highly demanded) change occurred in 2019, when a major amendment to the RES Support Act entered into force and brought a partial breaking of the stop state⁸⁸.

The process itself:

- **Permitting processes in construction:** new RES can be built only within the area of construction - only on land, on which it is permitted by law - on the zoning plan of the municipality in the production areas and on building land. Thus, the process to obtain a building permit can start after the verification of the location issues.
- **The environment - impact assessment (EIA)**⁸⁹. In some case it can result in a long, uncertain and expensive process that hamper the project realization.
- **Energy sector - certificate for the construction of plant:** The key document in the field of energy legislation, which must be of interest to the future producer, is the certificate for construction of a plant. It is regulated by Act on Energy, which states that the new plant will be compliant with the National energy policy and meets the required criteria. It is issued by Ministry of Economy (60-90 days). The opinion of the distribution and of the transmission system operators must be included in the application.
- **Other necessary steps:** In addition, producers will conclude relevant contractual documentation and then will have to obtaining an energy business permit, issuing a pricing decision, performing a functional test following the operational rules of distribution systems operators.

The ability to meet all the technical and commercial conditions for the connection to the grid is the moment in the whole process, in which producers are currently struggling to succeed.

Nevertheless, the commitment to achieve a 19.2% share of RES in gross final energy consumption (11.89% in 2018) by 2030, will require a deviation from the run-in tracks.

7.2.2 Authorization for injection in the grid

Table 13: The process of connecting biomethane production equipment to the gas distribution network of SPP-D

	The customer	SPP-D	Duration
1. Initial communication	Sending preliminary input data for the biogas project and its connection to the distribution grid	Initial project negotiations	
		Policy info connecting biogas producers to the distribution grid	
		Elaboration of PFS	1 month

⁸⁸ See more at: <https://www.polacekpartners.sk/en/article/the-requirements-for-construction-of-renewable-energy-sources-in-slovakia-what-processes-must-the-investors-go-through>

⁸⁹ <https://www.slov-lex.sk/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/2006/24/20200721>

D1.1: Framework and value chain conditions affecting the biogas uptake in livestock farming

2. Preliminary Feasibility Study (PFS)	Request to connect biomethane plant to the distribution network	Preliminary optimal method of technical implementation	
3. tech and commercial terms of connection		Issuance of tech and commercial terms of connection (TPP)	30 days
4. Agreement on connection of biomethane plant	Acceptance of TPP by customers	Signing the Connection Agreement	From about 1 month
	Signing the Connection Agreement		
5. Project documentation and permits	Project documentation + zoning decision + building permit	Assessment and approval of project documentation and cost calculation by SPP-D	From about 6 months
	Agreement on connection of the biomethane plant with SPP-D grid		
6. Realisation of the connection	Approval decision for the connection and equipment of the biomethane producer		From about 6 months
7. Calculation of cost for establishing a connection	Application for allocation of distribution capacity	Assessment of costs by the distribution network operator	From about 1 month
		Possible calculation of actual costs from a forensic expert	
		Payment of 75% of the actual costs for establishing connection	
8. Conclusion of the distribution agreement	Signature of Distribution Agreement	Signature of Distribution Agreement	20 days
9. Filing the connection + test operation		Opening the main HUP gas valve	3 months
		Biomethane quality control	
10. Operation		Issuing confirmation: monthly amount of biomethane to the grid	
		Quality control of biomethane supplied to the distribution grid	

7.2.3 Incentives schemes

The support mechanisms in Slovakia are based mainly on feed-in-premiums, feed-in-tariffs, or tax exemptions. The investment in upgrading BGP to biomethane plant is relatively high. BGPs must finance the transformation themselves, or they can participate in the current call from the Recovery and Resilience Plan.

A call⁹⁰ from RRP was issued on December 6, 2022 with the aim of modernisation existing BGPs but not of upgrading them to biomethane plants. The maximum aid intensity in Bratislava region is 45% and in the other regions 60%. A project is eligible if all of the following conditions are met:

- at list 2,000 equivalent production hours in 2021 or 1,000 from 1/1/2022 to 6/30/2022.
- the implementation of the project can't reduce the installed capacity of plant by more than 5%.
- the subject of the project can be the modernization of only one existing biogas station. Plants using wastewater sludge or landfill gases are not eligible.

The result of the project implementation must be extending the life of the biogas station without reducing its power (>95% of the power before the intervention)

The actual implementation of the project must end by March 31, 2026 at the latest.

⁹⁰ <https://www.mhsr.sk/uploads/files/dlcsxg08.pdf?csrt=10033003497674058626>

At the moment, there are no other calls to fund the upgrade or modernisation of BGPs.

7.2.4 Related legal aspects

- **Using of biodegradable municipal waste (BMW):** A critical point in the support of biogas and biomethane production is the lack of connection between the Act on RES and the legislation on waste. The valorisation of BMW should occur, and therefore it would be appropriate to amend the legislation so that the financial resources can be better used in the production of biomethane. The use of waste organic matter, including the use of agricultural, industrial and food waste can reduce the use of energy crops with energy security benefits. Currently, composting plants receive incentives for BMW management.
- **Handling of digestate:** already mentioned in the above text
- **Permitting at building authorities:** Currently, each municipal building authority is governed by different rules and principles when permitting construction or expansion of BGP/BMP. This significantly complicates the predictability of processes.
- **Calorific value of biomass:** The URSO's Decree no. 490/2009 Coll., establishes details on the support of renewable energy sources, high-efficiency cogeneration and biomethane⁹¹. The decree requires adding calorific value of biomass in kWh/t in a specific table, although BGPs don't have such information and the proposition on its calculation doesn't exist yet.
- **Requirement of holding tanks under fermenters:** The Decree of the Ministry of the Environment (MoE) no. 200/2018 Coll., regarding the treatment of pollutants, emergency plans and water deterioration⁹², is effective from July 15, 2018 and applies without exception to all BGPs, even those already existing. Before then, according with respective Decree of MoE 100/2005 Coll.1, plants were not required to follow this obligation.
- **The length and unpredictability of the EIA process:** already mentioned in the above text.
- **Inclusion of the BMP in the screening procedure:** MoE SR expressed the opinion (12/09/2022) that, according with Art. 54 Act 24/2006 Coll⁹³, that BMP should participate in the screening procedure but they are in the "List of proposed activities subject to environmental impact assessment". On the other hand, SBA suggests that the transformation of BGP or the realization of new BMP should not be subject to additional environmental investigation proceedings.
- **Connection pipelines & fragmentation of land ownership:** connection pipes are expensive (approx. 100€/m) and SPP-D reimburses 75% of the costs for its construction up to a length of 4 km; above this length, the entire remaining part is financed only by BMP. Moreover, field ownership is very fragmented and pipes often cross dozens of unidentified owners' fields. Connections realized by SPP-D in the public interest would help both problems.
- **The Technical Conditions of SPP – D, a.s.**⁹⁴:

⁹¹ <https://www.slov-lex.sk/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/2009/490/20200101>

⁹² <https://www.slov-lex.sk/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/2018/200/20180715>

⁹³ <https://www.slov-lex.sk/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/2006/24/20200721.html>

⁹⁴ <https://www.spp-distribucia.sk/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Technickepodmienky1112012.pdf>

- *Demonstration of hygienic safety:* The producer has to demonstrate the hygienic safety of the biomethane before starting its transfer to the distribution network; SPP-D has the right to disconnect or interrupt the distribution for hygienic reasons. More details on under which circumstances this point will be applied and which sample's parameters are needed.
- *Biomethane propanization:* BMP plants are required to add propane to the gas before injecting it in the grid in order to raise its heating value beyond the value set in Annex1. The use of a fossil fuel reduces the value of biomethane and requires additional investments. The solution would be to eliminate the need for propanization for high-pressure grid connections.
- *Connecting the BMP to the medium-pressure gas pipeline:* It is possible to connect plants only to the high-pressure network (connection point identified by SPP-D). The possibility to connect to medium pressure pipelines should be evaluate, also considering that only 30 out of 76 existing BGPs can be connected to a high-pressure (source SPP-D survey)

7.2.5 Policy priorities

Among the policy priorities identified by Slovak Biogas Association as via the interviews are:

- Simplification, elimination of bureaucracy, transparency as well as short-circuiting of the authorization process. Specifically:
 - allow concurrency of steps in screening procedure instead of succession to reduce time;
 - create detailed and binding guidelines of the Ministry of Environment for local officers
 - Change some reference values about the EIA procedure that are not thought for BGPs.
- Appropriately index the feed-in-tariffs to reflect current costs of BGPs;
- Apply tax of excess income only to BGP with installed capacity over 1 MW;
- Investigate quantities of waste, manure and slurry among producers and assess their proximity to existing BGP and their processing capacity. The same can apply to unused agricultural land;
- Approve an exception for the storage of dangerous liquid substances with high COD and BOD as the only harmful substance prohibited from being placed in a holding tank in the Decree No. 100/2005 Coll. of the Slovak Ministry of Environment;
- Carry out the construction of the connection pipeline to the gas grid in the name of SPP-D, and as a line construction in the public interest;
- Eliminate the need for propanization when connecting BMS to a high-pressure gas network;
- Individually assess the connection to medium pressure gas grid for each biomethane station;
- Valorisation of digestate as fertilizer to boost its commercialization and use.
- Adjust incentives so it can be used appropriately

7.3 Socioeconomic aspects

7.3.1 Economic aspects

A new, governmental FiT was approved on January 31, 2023. Moreover, the Government has adopted the Regulation No. 38/2023 Coll. introducing a cap on market revenues. Therefore, a 90% tax rate will be applied on revenues of BGPs over 240 EUR/MWh. As a result, operators of BGPs,

being out of the state purchase system, will face a lower FiT but also the cap on their revenues. However, one should take into account that they had to decide on the withdrawal from the state purchase system by the end of January 2022, when intentions to significantly increase FiT or introduce any cap were not known. By doing this, operators were trying to cover their increased costs and accumulate a financial profit to create a fund for the modernization or transformation of BGPs to biomethane plants (BMPs). These changes can heavily affect the investments on material and technologies recently carried on by Many operators. Therefore, a useful solution would be to extend the applicability of the Regulation No. 39/2023 Coll. to all BGPs, i.e., setting the governmental FiT also to those BGPs which are already out of the State purchase system.

It is questionable whether a new FiT will be sufficiently motivating to reactivate the production in the already shut down BGPs due to necessary investments in technology, the last years bad harvest of crops and the lack of waste sources.

7.3.2 Social aspects

The operation of BGP/BMP is more expensive in comparison to other RES, but it brings many other benefits. For instance, continuous production of electricity, supply of electricity at peak hours, and potential provision of ancillary services for the network operator, which will enable a further construction of new, interruptible RES. Furthermore, there are deliveries of biomethane to gas network, heating of nearby villages or buildings, a source of high-quality fertiliser, and the capture of methane from livestock excrement and biodegradable waste. These advantages should be converted into economic benefits. Reducing emissions from agricultural production, waste management and supplying CO₂ neutral to negative energy should be financially privileged. The produced organic fertilisers should be financially competitive with artificial/chemical fertilisers that have a cheap application.

In Slovakia, there is a general public-wide acceptance of the renewable energy projects implementation. However, at the local level, when it comes to a specific project, certain resistance from the local population appears – NIMBY affect - people usually support renewable energy only if the facility is not supposed to be in their proximity.⁹⁵

The direct positive impact of BGPs on employment is small as they operate with high degree of automation (1-2 qualified employees and service personnel are sufficient for their operation). The indirect positive impact of BGPs can also be perceived as they provide farmers with a stable sale of production. The other positive indirect impact on employment are BGPs using the heat produced– e.g. for the greenhouses for tomato production, providing jobs mostly for locals

7.4 Stakeholders' priorities

The **small livestock farmers** (1-man-farms farm in most cases cows), but also horses from 40-60pcs. Given the high prices of electricity and heat, some of them do consider the possibility to realize a biogas plants. They would like to be self-sufficient/reduce the farm energy consumption or even to earn money selling biogas/methane or electricity to the grid. To get a better fertilizer is another reason why they would consider to realize the biogas plant.

The idea is more appealing to **small cooperatives** (13-16 employees, out of which is 30-50% female) where from 350 (cows) - 600 (sheep) pieces of animals are farmed (on 400 Ha of permanent grassland) and e.g., wheat, rye, rape, maize/corn, peas, lucerne is cultivated (on circa

⁹⁵ Marián KULLA, Ladislav NOVOTNÝ, Loránt PREGI: [The role and perception of biogas in the energy transformation](#)

350 Ha) at the same time. They do have an opportunity to obtain agricultural by-products/subproducts either from their own production (e.g., milk whey 125m³/year) or from the other nearby farmers (hay). The electricity consumption of the above-mentioned cooperatives is about 180 MWh/year and around 60,000 litres of diesel oil per year. To reduce the farm energy consumption or even earn money selling biogas/methane or electricity to the grid are the main reasons when considering the realization of their own biogas plan. The barriers that hindered/hinder it, was either village residents' disagreement or insufficient support/incentives.

Biogas plants cooperating with the agriculture cooperatives (35 employee, 1,000 pcs of cattle and 160 ha of arable land - rye (hay) - 800 tons/year, silage corn – 1,200 tons/year, grasses – 2,000 tons/ year with the consumption of 160,000 litres of diesel oil per year) or agriculture cooperative with biogas plant/s (bigger group of circa 8 companies/farms engaged in crop and livestock farming in both conventional and organic farming systems with two biogas plants included; 60 employees - 20% female/80% male, 1,000 pcs of cattle & 2,000 pcs of sheep; 3,900 ha of arable land - wheat, barley, oats, rye, spelt, triticale, silage maize (2022 - 800 ha), arable grass, clover, mustard, flax, legume-cereal mixtures, permanent grassland...; electricity consumption of 300 MWh (per group), farmyards with two BGPs (702,611 kWh/year/both), diesel 435,000 l (per group), the biogas producers, would go for the realisation of biogas plant again, or even recommend the biomethane station realisation. The main reasons why are the same as above: earn money selling biogas/methane or electricity to the grid; reduce the farm energy consumption; get better fertilizer; but also, to implement a circular economy best practice. This kind of plant do have the opportunity to obtain large quantities of many different types of by-products such as milk whey, distillery stillage, potato peelings, soya lecithin etc. This guarantee a continue, well balanced (where manure is 5-40% of the input) feed to the digester. The prevalent use of biogas is for CHP where the excess heat can be sold to the nearby villages through pipelines. The digestate is mostly used to fertilize the fields.

From the point of view of biogas producers, they find the authorisation process inadequate, too bureaucratic, too long and too demanding, especially the environmental impact assessment (EIA). The views of legislators and permitting authorities vary, largely depending on personal sympathies or antipathies. The legislation is not set properly and clearly when it comes to biogas/biomethane stations – e.g., BGPs are subjects to controls pressure standards set by the legislation as for conventional gas, but biogas stations operate at considerably less pressure. Also, the constant changes in legislation go hand in hand with the uncertainty for biogas producers. The state support and incentives are insufficient – e.g., smaller biogas stations should be supported (less than 1MWh), the unclear calls' wording, subsequent cancellation or modification of calls after they are announced etc. The financial institutions are unwilling to invest in biogas business.

From the authorisation office's perspective – the authorisation process is adequate to the complexity and impact of such a plant and the public officers have the scientific basis for a complete techno-economic evaluation of a biogas plant. What's needed is to awareness raising in this topic – field visits to biogas plant (for public officers to know how it works in practice), consultation with the existing BGPs, exchange of good practices from abroad etc. Also, clear guidelines for the officers assessing these authorisations are missing, especially on biomethane.

7.5 Overall assessment

At the moment, there is a pessimistic mood in the biogas sector, and hesitation to invest. The investor has no guarantee of return on his investment, as no operating support (or at least a minimum guaranteed price) is planned. Moreover, the investor is unlikely to benefit even from the current high energy prices, due to the tax of excessive income from the sale of produced electricity.

From the survey, conducted by the SBA in September 2022, the answers to the question, "What would help your BGP to overcome an unfavourable situation?" were all about the need to have a higher, stable and guaranteed price for the energy produced.

BGPs are looking for new opportunities to establish themselves on the Slovak energy market even after the end of the guaranteed purchase price for electricity. A possibility is to expand the operation of the heating business, another one is further purification of biogas into biomethane to inject it in the existing gas distribution systems or to produce bioCNG and bioLNG; as in other countries, the biomethane use in transport is particularly promising.

Also, there is a big opportunity to use, process biodegradable municipal waste (BMW) and thus reduce its carbon footprint. The vast majority of state aid is directed towards the processing of MSW through composting plants, which do not exploit its energy potential at all.

8. Country: Belgium

In general, it is relevant to differentiate between Belgium's two non-urban regions, Flanders and Wallonia, which exhibit differences in terms of energy-related policies, the authorization processes for the instalment of biogas systems, and the characteristics of their farming sectors.

8.1 State of biogas and biomethane in livestock farming

With a large agricultural sector and an increasing amount of unutilized manure, the production of biogas from livestock manure has the potential to make a significant impact in Belgium. The Belgian livestock system mainly consists of cattle, swine and poultry (EC, 2021)⁹⁶. According to Eurostat (2022)⁹⁷, Belgium ranks fifth in the EU-27 in terms of livestock per capita. Therefore, Belgium has an outstanding manure potential.

The Figure 28 compare the distribution of feedstocks per region in terms of energy input along with their estimated biogas potential in 2030. In Flanders, animal manure is currently the predominant feedstock (49%), while in Wallonia, agriculture residues are the primary feedstock (41%), while in Wallonia, agriculture residues are the primary feedstock and manure represents 35% of the total (Julien et al., 2021)⁹⁸.

In 2019, only 11% of Belgium's total bioenergy consumption came from biogas (IEA, 2021)⁹⁹. However, its total supply of biogas was 0.8 GJ per capita, in line with the median among IEA members. In 2021, Belgium's total biogas production was 2.809 GWh (EBA, 2022)¹⁰⁰. Belgium's total energy supply (TES) relied on fossil fuels, which accounted for 70% of the TES (IEA, 2021). Renewable energy sources only accounted for 7.8% of the Belgian TES in 2019, with biomass being the largest contributor among them (at 70% of the total RES supply) (IEA, 2021).

The Deep Dive study by Climact, Valbiom, Biogas-e and Gas.be included several reports about the potential of biogas and biomethane in Belgium (see Schmitt, 2021; Tessens and Vergote, 2021;

Figure 28. Main feedstocks in Belgium⁹⁸.

⁹⁶ European Commission (2021). Statistical Factsheet – Belgium. Available at : https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-12/agri-statistical-factsheet-be_en_0.pdf

⁹⁷ Eurostat (2022). Animal populations by NUTS 2 regions. Last updated 12/10/2022. Available at : https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/agr_r_animal/default/table?lang=en

⁹⁸ Julien, M., Lemmens, P-W., Squilbin, O., Linden, C. V. (2021). Deep Dive Study for Biomethane in Belgium: WP4 – Externalities – Final report. Climact. Gas.be. Available at: <https://www.gas.be/fr/deepdive-studie-potentieel-biomethaan-belgi%C3%AB>

⁹⁹ IEA (2021). IEA Bioenergy Implementation of bioenergy in Belgium – 2021 update. Available at: https://www.ieabioenergy.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/CountryReport2021_Belgium_final.pdf

¹⁰⁰ EBA (European Biogas Association) (2022a). Statistical Report 2022: Tracking biogas and biomethane deployment across Europe.

Julien et al., 2021)^{101 102 98}. These studies estimated that in Flanders and Wallonia, respectively, the gross biogas potential is 7.2 and 7.9 TWh per year, and the net biomethane potential around 5 and 5.7 TWh. If this potential would be fully exploited, biomethane could contribute to increasing the share of renewables by 2030 with 1,6% in Flanders and 4,4% in Wallonia, respectively.

On the regional level, Flanders had 137 installations producing biogas in 2021 (EBA, 2022)¹⁰⁰, about half of which using agricultural feedstock types as their primary input. However, only 14% of the region's biogas production potential is utilised today (Tessens & Vergote, 2021)¹⁰². In Wallonia, there were 52 biogas plants in 2021 (EBA, 2022), of which over 30 using agricultural feedstocks from farmers (ValBiom, 2021)¹⁰³. Of the latter, 15 were small plants (i.e., producing the equivalent of 50 kW or less) in farms, mostly using manure from milk cows. Nevertheless, most micro-scale plants, which represent the most common type of installation in livestock farming, are in Flanders; the BioEnergy Farm project estimated that Belgium had 70 micro-scale digesters¹⁰⁴.

Growth in Belgium's biogas sector took off after the introduction of the National Green Certificate Scheme in 2001 (EBA, 2022). Over the last decade, the biogas in livestock farming industry expanded significantly thanks to the introduction of smaller-scale digesters in the market. However, technical and efficiency issues led some farmers to shut down their micro installations between 2015 and 2018; since then, there has been a shift to higher capacities (20 – 85 kW) (EBA, 2022).

Focusing on biomethane, the estimated gross potential production in Belgium is 15,6 TWh by 2030, i.e. about 16% of the current supply from natural gas distribution grids (Tessens & Vergote, 2021)¹⁰². There are currently only 8 biomethane plants in Belgium (EBA, 2022). In 2021, Belgium produced 156 GWh of biomethane, of which around 150 GWh in Wallonia, but considering that 5 plants started operating during 2021, biomethane production is estimated to reach 350 GWh by 2023 (EBA, 2022).

8.2 Legal and policy framework

8.2.1 Authorization process for the instalment of biogas systems

In Flanders, permits for biogas plant construction are on hold due to recent court decisions on nitrogen regulations and recent measures aimed at reducing nitrogen emissions in farming, which has been strongly opposed by farmer organizations and technology suppliers, who advocate for decoupling licensing for digesters from the nitrogen framework.

The following table provides more information on the “standard” authorization process for the regions of Wallonia and Flanders:

¹⁰¹ Schmitt, M. (2021). Comment développer au mieux la biométhanisation en Wallonie ? Feuille de route pour le développement raisonné de la biométhanisation en Wallonie - Rapport final de l'étude de planification - WP5. Available at: <https://www.gas.be/fr/deepdive-studie-potentieel-biomethaan-belgi%C3%AB>

¹⁰² Tessens, S. and Vergote, T. (2021). Deep Dive study Green Gas Platform: a roadmap for anaerobic digestion by 2050. Rapport WP 0 - 2. Available at: <https://www.biogas-e.be/node/1039>

¹⁰³ ValBiom (2021). Panorama de la Biométhanisation en Wallonie: Édition 2021. Available at: https://www.valbiom.be/sites/default/files/tool/file/panorama_biometh_2021.pdf

¹⁰⁴ BioEnergy Farm (n.d.). Micro-scale digesters in practice. Available at: <https://www.bioenergyfarm.eu/en/info-for-policymakers/msd-in-practice/#>

Table 14. Biogas plants' authorization process and authorities involved

Region	Authorization by	Types of permits ¹⁰⁵	Types and maximum allowed amount of substrates	Timeframe	Overall process steps
Wallonia	The respective municipality	Class I	Production of biogas and digestate using > 500 t/day of substrates (incl. manure)	140 days ± 30 days	Application for an environmental permit + Environmental Impact Study
		Class II	Production of biogas and digestate using <= 500 t/day of substrates (incl. manure)	90 days ± 30 days	Application for an environmental permit + <i>possible</i> Environmental Impact Study (at the request of the Administration)
Flanders	Environmental permit: Depends on the type of Class (see next column) Construction permit: The respective municipality	Class I: most disruptive environmental impact (provincial permit)	Biogas installations in farms fall under classes 1 and 2. The type of permit needed will depend on (i) the source of the manure, (ii) the size of the installation, (iii) the location of the installation (industry vs agricultural area) (De Dobbelaere et al., 2020b) ¹⁰⁶	max. 4.5 months	1) Submission to the the relevant provincial administration ('provinciebestuur') 2) After the application, a public inquiry and an advisory round are organized. 3) If the permit is refused, an appeal can be made to the Flemish government.
		Class II: less disruptive environmental impact (municipal permit)		max. 3.5 months	1) Submission to the municipal council (the Board of Mayor and Aldermen) 2) After the application, a public inquiry and an advisory round are organized. 3) If the permit is refused, an appeal can be made to the provincial administration.
		Class III: least disruptive activity		N.A.	Only a notification to the municipal council is mandatory

In Wallonia, obtaining a permit to build a biogas plant typically takes up to 6 months. Before submitting a request, the farmer must obtain an opinion from the Transversal Biomass Committee, which comprises representatives from various public administration departments and a climate expert. The opinion must be issued within 30 days; otherwise, it is considered favourable. The authorization process for larger biogas plants is more time-consuming.

¹⁰⁵ For Wallonia, a third class of permits may exist for biogas plants that use substrates which are not legally considered as “waste”, with a 15t/day maximum limit of substrates. Thus, it should be noted, that it does not apply to the use of livestock manure in Wallonia, as manure is classified as waste according to the Walloon law on the topic.

¹⁰⁶ More specific factors that determine whether the permit falls under class 2, and thus the administrative procedure is simplified, include: (i) using farm-owned manure, so that the installation is not regarded as a manure processing installation; (ii) using also other feedstocks sourced from the own farm (e.g., harvest residues), so that they are not considered waste; (iii) keeping biogas production below 100 Nm³/hour. More information in (De Dobbelaere et al., 2020b). De Dobbelaere, A., Leenknecht, J., Vandendriessche, S., Verleden, I., Decorte, M., Winternitz, K., Meers, E., Vergote, I., Bamelis, L., Snauwaert, E., Demeulemeester, M. (2020). Module 3: Wetgeving & steunmaatregelen voor kleinschalige vergisting. Part of Pocket Power project. Inagro, Biogas-E, UGent, DLV. Available at: <https://inagro.be/sites/default/files/media/files/2021-09/pocketvergisting-praktijkvoorbeelden.pdf>

8.2.2 Incentives schemes

Overall, the supportive measures for the production of renewable energy in Belgium include **investment subsidies**, **green certificates** and **tax reductions** (IEA, 2021)¹⁰⁷.

In the Wallonia and Brussels Region, green certificates are issued to renewable energy producers, who must purchase an annual quota of certificates proportional to the volume of electricity they sell (IEA 2021). However, the Walloon government severely reduced the number of certificates issued for biogas plants after 2022.

In 2003, an **Energy Fund** was established in Wallonia to support demonstration projects and electricity production from renewable sources. A few years later, a Decree on Biofuel Product Norms introduced a registration system for biofuels sold in Belgium, which allows for the verification of the incorporation of sustainable biofuels. Additionally, since 2014, capital grants of up to 15% of the eligible investments in renewable energy, including that produced from biomass, are provided. Since 2017, the federal **Energy Transition Fund** funds energy-related research, development, and innovation (IEA, 2022). Each year, a call for project proposals is organised, offering subsidies ranging from €100,000 to €5 million (PwC, 2016-2022).

Following Belgium's first biomethane plant in 2018, the country's policy has shifted to include biomethane production into existing support systems. In Wallonia, the subsidies for green electricity were extended to make biomethane production also eligible, while the Flemish government decided in 2019 to extend its registry system for renewable electricity to include renewable gas. While there are no support measures in place for the injection of biomethane into the grid in Flanders, support schemes exist for the use of biogas in CHP's (Julien et al., 2021)⁹⁸.

Meeting Belgium's aforementioned biomethane production potential by 2030 is estimated to require support amounting to over €300 million/year in both Flanders and Wallonia, in order to bridge the cost difference between producing biomethane and its fossil alternative (Julien et al., 2021)⁹⁸.

8.2.3 Related legal aspects

At the Flemish level, a key element of current manure policy is MAP 6, the 6th Action Program for the period 2019-2022, and the Manure Decree (VLM, 2021)¹⁰⁸. In **MAP 6**, Flanders set out the ambition to take measures to reduce nutrient losses from agriculture and improve water quality. This commitment is applied in legislation through the Manure Decree. MAP 6 states stricter measures in areas with poorer water quality (e.g., the additional sowing of catch crops), and stricter fertilization standards regarding nitrogen. Another important element is the **Manure Bank**, which is used to monitor compliance with manure legislation. The Manure Bank carries out administrative checks, risk-based company audits, targeted site checks and nitrate residue controls. Additionally, the Manure Bank creates a database including data on the number of animals, the amount of manure in storage, data about manure transport, the manure and soil analyses, and the use of fertilizer.

8.2.4 Policy priorities

Since 2019, the **National Renewable Energy Action Plan** of Belgium is in force, as required by the EU Directive 2009/28/EC, establishing renewable energy, energy efficiency and GHG cuts targets (IEA, 2022). The renewable energy share should reach approximately 13% of the gross total energy

¹⁰⁷ IEA (2021). IEA Bioenergy Implementation of bioenergy in Belgium – 2021 update. Available at: https://www.ieabioenergy.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/CountryReport2021_Belgium_final.pdf

¹⁰⁸ VLM (Vlaamse Landmaatschappij) (2021). Mestrapport 2021. Brussel. Available at: <https://www.vlm.be/nl/themas/regelgeving/regelgeving-mestbank/besluiten/Mestdecreet>

consumption of the country, a target which was accompanied by a variety of supportive measures, including: green certificates schemes and tax incentives for investments in renewable energy.

Following the pandemic crisis, **Belgium's recovery and resilience plan** aims to accelerate the transition towards a more sustainable economy (EC, 2022)¹⁰⁹ by supporting the development of non-fossil-based hydrogen and carbon markets and reforming fossil fuel subsidies (IEA, 2022, EC 2022). There are, however, no specific Belgian targets for biomethane production yet (EBA, 2022).

8.3 Socioeconomic aspects

8.3.1 Economic aspects

In 2021, the population of cattle in Belgium was over 2.3M heads, according to Statbel (2022)¹¹⁰. The vast majority of cattle farms had over 150 animals. The total amount of pigs was over 6M, the majority of farms having over 1500 animals. Average farm sizes have more than doubled in both regions since 1980 (The Brussels Times, 2021)¹¹¹, while the average monetary output from agricultural production increased from 166,676 euros in 2005 to 241,766 euros in 2019. This went hand in hand with a decreasing number of farms.

In terms of financing, interviewees reported that financing a biogas plant in Belgium can pose several challenges, particularly in obtaining a loan. Smaller biogas plants, particularly those focused on cow manure, are considered less financially risky and can obtain a loan decision from the bank with a week, given that the necessary information, including a reliable financial plan and environmental permits, is provided. For large plants, it may take several months for the bank to have the ability to assess and decide on the investment. There are also examples of projects that use alternative sources of funding like crowdsourcing¹¹². Although payback times depend on the size of the installation and on the farm's energy consumption, previous studies provided examples of Belgian farmers that reported pay-back times of 5 to 7 years for biogas installations of between 10 and 30 kW of installed power (De Dobbelaere et al., 2015; De Dobbelaere et al., 2020)¹¹³. The investment costs for a small plant of 9.7 kW were reported to be between €90-95,000, including CHP (turnkey) technology but excluding costs of obtaining a license or building an external manure storage, if this is not already available in the farm. The main cited financial benefit is the reduction of the energy bill, often to the point of self-sufficiency.

8.3.2 Social aspects

According to the interviewees, most farmers are male, but gender equality in decision-making improves when both men and women are involved in running the farm. Family farms are often run

¹⁰⁹ European Commission (2022). Belgium's recovery and resilience plan. Available at: https://commission.europa.eu/business-economy-euro/economic-recovery/recovery-and-resilience-facility/belgiums-recovery-and-resilience-plan_en

¹¹⁰ Statbel (2022). Article – "72.4% of the agricultural labour force comes from the family circle". Available at : <https://statbel.fgov.be/en/news/724-agricultural-labour-force-comes-family-circle>

¹¹¹ The Brussels Times (2021). "Belgium has 70% fewer farms now than in 1980". Available at: <https://www.brusselstimes.com/124480/belgium-has-70-fewer-farms-now-than-in-1980>

¹¹² For more info, see www.econova.com/fr/projet/walvert-estinnes.

¹¹³ De Dobbelaere, A., De Keulenaere, B., De Mey, J., Lebuf, V., Meers, E., Ryckaert, B., Schollier, C., Van Driessche, J., Demeulemeester, M. (2015). Small-scale anaerobic digestion: Case studies in Western Europe. *enerpedia*

De Dobbelaere, A., Leenknecht, J., Vandendriessche, S., Verleden, I., Decorte, M., Winternitz, K., Meers, E., Vergote, I., Bamelis, L., Snauwaert, E., Demeulemeester, M. (2020). Module 6: Praktijkvoorbeelden. Part of Pocket Power project. Inagro, Biogas-E, UGent, DLV. Available at: <https://inagro.be/sites/default/files/media/files/2021-09/pocketvergisting-praktijkvoorbeelden.pdf>

by a male-female couple, with men focusing on technical aspects while women handle administrative tasks like exporting digestate and managing budgets. Women are more interested in investing in biogas systems due to the cost-saving opportunities they offer but are less likely to be involved in livestock farming due to its physical demands.

Concerning social acceptance, one of the interviewees reported that micro-biogas systems tend to be socially accepted, as they do not involve importing manure and can mitigate potential odour issues. In contrast, larger biogas plants often face opposition due to concerns over explosions, smells, traffic, and pollution. Farmers try to address these objections through open communication with local residents, but the effectiveness of these efforts depends on factors such as timing and whether the objections come from within the community.

8.4 Stakeholders' priorities

This section presents the results of the interviews conducted with stakeholders involved in the Belgian value chain for biogas in livestock farming, highlighting current challenges and opportunities. The interviewees consist of a bioenergy advisor based in Wallonia, a public officer in Flanders, a representative from a financial institution and a sales responsible from a leading technology provider.

Market Demand and Maturity: The demand for biogas systems using animal waste is high, and farmers are interested in the technology, especially in small-scale installations for electricity production, and rising energy prices make this option appealing. The market for micro-biogas plants still lacks strong competition, despite the widespread installation of mono-digesters on farms and the fact that Bioelectric's entry into the market made the technology accessible to small farms, which previously had the perception that the technology was only available to large farms. However, until four years ago, there were some issues involving micro digesters, resulting from various aspects of the process (i.e., from manure processing to CHP). Consequently, some farmers stopped using this type of plants, whereas bankers became more hesitant to issue loans for similar installations.

Installation Process and Authorization Barriers: Installation of micro biogas plants in Wallonia takes around two years, with financing being the most challenging phase due to concerns about reliability and existing farm debt. Feasibility study and authorization phases follow standard procedures. Construction takes an average of six months but can vary significantly between farms. In Flanders, the main barrier to wider adoption of biogas technology is the permitting process. The difficulty in obtaining permits poses a significant barrier to farmers considering investments in biogas plants. Due to court decisions and regulations concerning nitrogen emissions, the granting of permits for manure processing and biogas production activities is currently stalled. The process of obtaining permits for biogas installations is also considered too complex for most farmers and breeders.

Financing Situation for Biogas Plants: Financing biogas plants depends on the type of plant, differing between large co-digestion plants and smaller co-digestion and mono-digestion plants. Smaller plants are viewed as less financially risky due to their lower investment size and cost-saving potential, while larger plants present more complexity and uncertainty due to technical complexities, changing input streams, and revenue fluctuations from energy sales. KBC grants loans for replacement investments, co-generators, or biomethane plants in the case of large co-digesting plants. The bank's policy for financing new large co-digesting plants is stricter, and they require a good track record from the borrower. For smaller plants, the bank has a more lenient policy resulting in a higher acceptance rate, provided the borrower contributes some capital.

Obstacles related to the financing of biogas plants in livestock farming:

- **The reliability of the documentation provided by the borrowers:** Banks deem it crucial to ascertain the credibility of the financial plan, particularly with regards to estimates of biogas yields, projected input costs, and expected revenue from digestate and energy.

- **The capacity of farmers/farm managers:** Given the complexity of the biological process involved in co-digestion and biogas production, it is imperative that farmers possess knowledge of the critical steps involved in the biological process and the market. Additionally, it is important for the farmers to have the necessary skills to address any technical issues that may arise in the biogas installation to prevent potential consequences.
- **Risks:** Investments in biogas plants are always subject to a high degree of uncertainty, given the unpredictability of revenues derived from the selling of energy. For large co-digestion plants, one of the significant risks is related to changing the mix of input streams, which can have negative effects on biogas production. Insurers also have strict policies arising from their concern of the potential self-burning of the stored digestate.
- **Input quality:** Manure quality is important for biogas plant profitability. Factors such as livestock grazing practices can affect the quality of manure used. Pig manure has a high nitrogen content, making it harder to ferment than cow manure, and may require additional input streams or separation to improve its quality.

Enablers to overcome barriers to adoption. Technology providers like Bioelectric help reduce the input quality risk for farmers by testing their manure for free before installing the plants. They also avoid over-dimensioning the plant relative to farm size to maximise the feasibility of the investment and reduce payback times. Further, they support farmers in obtaining the necessary permits and offering guidance to develop a business plan when approaching banks for a loan. In addition, while large plants may face opposition from neighbours due to bad smells, small plants do not increase the smell in farms that are already storing manure.

Scientific knowledge for biogas plant evaluation: Research has been carried out on the technical and economic aspects of implementing biogas installations on farms, providing a scientific basis to farmers, bankers and public officers alike. However, further studies are required to investigate the nitrogen emissions resulting from biogas plants, as well as from digestate storage and fertilizer use. Bank employees do not need to have extensive scientific knowledge of the anaerobic digestion process, but they should have expertise to identify financial risks and evaluate return on investment, since unexpected events in the complex biological process of anaerobic digestion can lead to financial consequences, making it challenging to predict returns and payback periods.

Suggestions: Most suggestions centered on the need to improve the efficiency of the authorization process in Flanders. These included (i) making clear guidelines more widely available to entrepreneurs and investors and (ii) easing the process for small-scale installations on farms that primarily engage in agricultural activities and have farm-specific flows; more specifically, it was suggested that such deployments should only require a notification to authorities. Another type of suggestion to encourage wider adoption was to increase awareness of biogas technology.

8.5 Overall assessment

Belgium has a strong national socioeconomic framework that supports the development and growth of the biogas and biomethane sector. The country has notable developments in Flanders and Wallonia, with each region offering unique strengths and challenges, as presented in Table 15

Table 15. Overall assessment of Belgium national socioeconomic framework

Region	Current status of biogas installations	Installation		Overall assessment
		Strengths	Challenges	
Wallonia	>50 biogas plants, of which 40 “agricultural” and 12-15 micro plants in farms using manure 5 biomethane plants	A strong agricultural sector and several projects focusing on biogas/biomethane	The lengthy installation process for micro-biogas plants, taking an average of two years, and 6-month construction	Biogas production in Belgium has gained traction in recent years, particularly with smaller co-digestion and mono-digestion plants utilizing cow manure. However, financing larger co-digestion plants presents complexity and elevated levels of uncertainty. The capacity and knowledge of farmers/farm managers, the reliability of documentation provided by borrowers, and the unpredictability of revenue from energy sales pose challenges in financing biogas plants. Legislation at the Flemish level is currently very restrictive, and input quality, particularly for pig manure, can affect the financial viability of the project. In addition, the threat of potential opposition from neighbors remains present, especially against larger plants. Nevertheless, Belgium presents a high potential for biogas generation from livestock manure, which currently remains untapped.
		Presence of larger agricultural biogas plants, and the ability of micro-biogas plants to meet livestock farms' energy consumption needs.	Suboptimal efficiency of micro-biogas plants	
		A standard and streamlined environmental permit application procedure	Difficulty in obtaining financing from banks and green certificates	
Flanders	>80 biogas plants; large presence of micro plants in farms using manure 3 biomethane plants	Short payback period for small plants	Longer payback period for larger installations	
		Well-established biogas and agricultural sectors with several biogas plants	Restrictive legislation and slow permit process	
		Higher acceptance rate of loans for smaller plants	Manure quality variation affecting financial viability	

9. Conclusions

The analysis carried on in the 6 target regions highlighted that the biogas and biomethane market development is not uniform across Europe and, as a consequence, stakeholders from different regions may have different needs and expectations.

Indeed, Denmark and Italy, that already have a good production level compared to their potential, are trying to further develop the social, economic and legal framework to reach their full potential in the next decades; to this end different policies are possible that imply an evolution in the biogas use.

To this end, there are some debates about changes in the legal framework and incentives for anaerobic digesters to provide new services. In particular it is possible to encourage the use of biomethane in the transport sector to replace fossil fuels, plan the power production to compensate the discontinuity of other RES and even absorb excess electricity to produce biomethane and feed it into the gas grid. Likely, a combination of these services will guarantee a better result.

The other Countries are trying to catch up and make biogas play its role in achieving the goals of the green deal drawing on the experience of countries where the market is more developed.

Despite major differences in the regulatory framework and in the market development, all the regions showed the need for many services for farmers. Indeed, all the Country analysis highlighted that a wide spread of the biogas and biomethane technologies, requires additional effort to disseminate knowledge and raise awareness and a range of services to support farmers and breeders in the realization of plants.

These services may include information on the technologies and the incentives, the evaluation of the potential or preliminary feasibility study, the support for the authorization process etc. and they will be developed together with the relevant stakeholders in the co-creation workshops that will be organized in WP2; to enhance their effectiveness, all the services will be shaped for each Alfa Hub considering the regional specificities that emerged in this study and the findings of the surveys on perception and acceptance of biogas (task T1.2).

The project

ALFA has the objective to help unlock the EU's biogas production potential by fostering the adoption of technologies using manure to produce biogas, thus helping increase the adoption of renewable energy sources in the EU and helping reduce emissions from untreated animal waste. The project will identify drivers and barriers for the uptake of biogas in the EU livestock farming industry and will support farmers from 6 EU countries (Italy, Denmark, Belgium, Slovakia, Greece and Spain) through its own co-created solutions, including financial, business, and technical support services as well as capacity-building seminars. In parallel, the project will develop an Engagement Platform to host tools that facilitate collaboration and knowledge exchange among industry actors and provide credible estimations of each farm's biogas potential, prospect profits, and environmental and social impacts. Moreover, ALFA will inform all relevant stakeholders via awareness-raising campaigns and policy recommendations, and will provide guidelines for replication of its results in other regions.

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